

Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36

Project:	Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT
Grant Agreement:	101094796 - HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Editors:	Katharine Sarikakis, Simon Haslauer (UNIVIE)
Authors:	<p>Policy Brief 1: Katharine Sarikakis, Yves Saint Clair Zogo, Grigorios Arkoumanis, Sarah Baumgartner, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou, Gentiana Ramadani, Simon Haslauer (UNIVIE)</p> <p>Policy Brief 2: Denise Amram, Jacopo Fortuna, Nicoletta Patti, Veronica Punzo, Roberta Romano (SSSA)</p> <p>Policy Brief 3: Marina Rossato Fernandes, Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR)</p> <p>Policy Brief 4: Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU)</p> <p>Policy Brief 5: Marcin Sobieszczanski, Asimina Koukou (UCA)</p> <p>Policy Brief 6: Mafalda Dâmaso, Anna Niutta (EUR), Antonios Vlassis, Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU), Ruken Doğu Erdede, Melis Behlil, Elif Akçalı (KHAS)</p>
Reviewers:	Fernando Ramos Arenas (UCM), Arianna Martinelli (SSSA), Apostolos Samaras (ELIAMEP), Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv (UW)

Object D7.14 Policy briefings deriving from
WP2-5 M36

WP WP7 (University of Vienna)

Deliverable Lead University of Vienna

Type R=report

Dissemination Level PU= public

Version 1.0

Funded by the
European Union

Metadata

Project	Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT
Acronym	REBOOT
Programme	Horizon Europe
Call	HORIZON-CL2-2022-HERITAGE-01
Grant Agreement No.	101094796
Project coordinator	Katharine Sarikakis (UNIVIE)
Licensing terms	CC-BY 4.0
DOI	https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831
Editors	Katharine Sarikakis, Simon Haslauer (UNIVIE)
Authors	Policy Brief 1: Katharine Sarikakis, Yves Saint Clair Zogo, Grigorios Arkoumanis, Sarah Baumgartner, Simon Haslauer, Gentiana Ramadani, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE) Policy Brief 2: Denise Amram, Jacopo Fortuna, Nicoletta Patti, Veronica Punzo, Roberta Romano (SSSA)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

	<p>Policy Brief 3: Marina Rossato Fernandes, Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR)</p> <p>Policy Brief 4: Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU)</p> <p>Policy Brief 5: Marcin Sobieszczanski, Asimina Koukou (UCA)</p> <p>Policy Brief 6: Mafalda Dâmaso, Anna Niutta (EUR), Antonios Vlassis, Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU), Ruken Doğu Erdede, Melis Behlil, Elif Akçalı (KHAS)</p>
Reviewers	Fernando Ramos Arenas (UCM), Arianna Martinelli (SSSA), Apostolos Samaras (ELIAMEP), Alicja Waszkiewicz-Raviv (UW)
Title	Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36
Deliverable No.	D7.14
WP No.	7
Deliverable Lead	University of Vienna
Type	Report
Dissemination Level	Public
Version	1.0
Keywords	Policy Brief, European Film Industry, Artificial Intelligence, children's rights, VOD, European film policy, European Union, XR
Language	English

CONTENTS

List of tables	4
The REBOOT project summary.....	5
Purpose of this document.....	6
Framing AI legal and ethical frontiers in the European film industry	7
Children’s rights in the digital era: take-away policy recommendations for the film industry.....	15
Streaming services and the competitiveness of the European Film industry in Europe and Latin America	26
Developing the outreach and impact of European audience film awards.....	38
Towards a Unified European Policy Framework for Cinema/XR’ Hybridization	48
The European Union as an Enabler of International Film Relations.....	61

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

LIST OF TABLES

Table 1: Selected national policies and initiatives facilitating the hybridization of cinema and XR examined in the REBOOT project.	52
Table 2: Selected EU-level audiovisual and digital policies pertinent to cinema/XR hybridization examined in the REBOOT project.	53
Table 3: Selected financial assistance and financed immersive initiatives examined in the REBOOT project.....	55

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

THE REBOOT PROJECT SUMMARY

This project aims to connect existing strengths, identify and overcome weaknesses, and plan for future competitiveness in the fields of policy, practice and experience. More concretely, the project's objectives are, firstly, to explore the long-standing strengths and pervasive gaps in European competitiveness and policies for competitiveness. This includes ways of measuring, analysing and evaluating the impact of policies and strategic pathways. Secondly, the project aspires to actively prepare for future audiences by exploring audience preferences and their generation, as well as modes of film content production. The latter are elements which today's youth will engage with in the coming decades as makers and consumers, as well as industry and policy leaders. Therefore, the consortium interrogates not only "what is" but also "what has been" and "what will be" from fresh perspectives.

REBOOT's ambition is to provide a full set of knowledge of the European film industry, which maximises its existing strengths, combined with strategic and tactical dimensions of action to optimise the potential held in European youth publics, understood both as emerging audiences and as citizens. Specifically, the ambition of the project combines several dimensions, which reinforce each other but are listed separately for analytical purposes (and in no particular order): a) increasing support for young people's engagement with European film; b) strengthening the place of the European Union (EU) in the global audiovisual economy, particularly in light of the rise of video on demand (VoD); c) supporting cultural diversity in the EU film industry; d) addressing the need for a different understanding of competitiveness and relevant indicators in this context; and e) recognising and supporting the importance for the EU of film and, more broadly, of the cultural and creative sector as a geopolitical asset.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

PURPOSE OF THIS DOCUMENT

This document contains Policy Briefs and Recommendations that emerged from WP2 – WP5 of the REBOOT project.

The following policy briefs are provided:

Framing AI legal and ethical frontiers in the European film industry

Authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Yves Saint Clair Zogo, Grigorios Arkoumanis, Sarah Baumgartner, Simon Haslauer, Gentiana Ramadani, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE)

Children’s rights in the digital era: take-away policy recommendations for the film industry

Authors: Denise Amram, Jacopo Fortuna, Nicoletta Patti, Veronica Punzo, Roberta Romano (SSSA)

Streaming services and the competitiveness of the European Film industry in Europe and Latin America

Authors: Marina Rossato Fernandes, Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR)

Developing the outreach and impact of European audience film awards

Authors: Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU)

Towards a Unified European Policy Framework for Cinema/XR Hybridization

Authors: Marcin Sobieszczanski, Asimina Koukou (UCA)

The European Union as an Enabler of International Film Relations

Authors: Mafalda Dâmaso, Anna Niutta (EUR), Antonios Vlassis, Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU), Ruken Doğu Erdede, Melis Behlil, Elif Akçalı (KHAS)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Policy Brief

January 2026

Framing AI Legal and Ethical Frontiers in the European Film Industry

Authors: Katharine Sarikakis, Yves Saint Clair Zogo, Grigorios Arkoumanis, Sarah Baumgartner, Simon Haslauer, Gentiana Ramadani, Angeliki Chatziefrimidou (UNIVIE)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Who is this aimed at

Relevant to the European Film Industry:

- EU and national policymakers
- Government and local Authorities
- Industry and professional associations
- AI developers and technology providers
- Trade unions and guilds representing creative and technical workers
- Educational and vocational institutions
- Platforms and Technology Industry

Key Messages

The Film industry is undergoing further technological transformation with the development and implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into every stage of filmmaking: from concept development to distribution, AI is redefining not only practices, but also possibly notions of *authorship, ownership and artistic labour*. AI use raises questions for the protection and recognition of human creativity, regulatory implications and furthermore crucial ethical questions for expression, authenticity, truth and connection in European film. This evolution offers on the one hand immense opportunities for efficiency, innovation and market expansion, but on the other hand it also raises structural and normative challenges that test the resilience of Europe's cultural and regulatory frameworks. The European Union has taken a leading stance in AI governance through the GDPR, the AI Act, and the Digital Single Market Directive, yet the *scope and translation* of these frameworks into the creative industries remains incomplete and uneven. If guided by a coherent *common* policy vision that integrates legal certainty, ethical responsibility and cultural inclusivity, AI can become not a threat but a catalyst - enhancing creativity, empowering artists and positioning the European film industry as a global exemplar of responsible innovation.

Introduction

The integration of AI into film production has profoundly altered the audiovisual creative process, challenging traditional notions of human labour, creativity and authenticity. The European Union (EU) has taken the lead in shaping a responsible AI policy framework, most notably through initiatives, such as the EU AI Act and the earlier White Paper on AI, among others, aiming to address fairness, transparency and accountability. While the Act promotes trustworthy, human-centric AI and safeguards, crucial aspects, such as health, safety, fundamental rights, democracy and the

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

environment, its implementation in the creative sector in general, and in the film sector, in particular, remains vague, fragmented and largely unmonitored leaving a regulatory gap. The AI Act introduces specific obligations for general-purpose AI (GPAI) models, including transparency requirements for training data, documentation of model capabilities and limits, and risk-mitigation processes for downstream users. For film-production contexts, this means that tools used for script generation, automated editing, facial-motion analysis or synthetic-media creation must provide accessible information about how they were trained and how they handle potentially infringing or biased content. Existing research highlights AI's potential to increase technical precision and productivity up to 75% and to democratise access to various tools for both major studios and independent creators, enhancing economic resilience and resource efficiency. Drawing upon in-depth EU regulation analysis, interviews with stakeholders and review of the literature, this policy brief maps existing regulation tensions related to AI in film production. Moreover, it examines the multifaceted impact of AI on the European film industry and provides concrete policy recommendations for the ethical implementation of AI in the film industry. We contend that, when grounded in ethical practices, AI can become a strategic asset for the European film industry-strengthening its global positioning by showcasing innovation, cultural relevance and a clear commitment to responsible media production.

Statement of the problem

The rapid integration of AI into European film production promises substantial efficiency gains but creates a legal and ethical vacuum that threatens core industry values (Liu et al., 2023). While the EU's 2024 AI Act establishes a common framework for AI systems, its provisions remain vague and unmonitored in the context of creative media, leaving filmmakers without clear standards for responsible use. This regulatory ambiguity is compounded by the absence of sector-specific guidelines, resulting in fragmented practices that fail to address fairness, transparency and accountability in film-related AI applications (Thomas, 2024).

Moreover, generative AI models train on massive datasets that often include copyrighted works without having secured consent by owners of intellectual property, raising serious misappropriation and authorship concerns for audiovisual creators (Oberting, 2024). The EU's text-and-data-mining (TDM) exception, originally designed for scholarly research, is now being stretched to permit commercial AI training, further blurring the line between lawful data use and infringement (Jiang et al., 2023; Khattak et al., 2025). Concurrently, AI-driven workflows risk deepening labour inequalities by privileging AI-savvy professionals while marginalising those lacking digital expertise (Yumeng & Xiao, 2025). The increasing use of synthetic actors, voice cloning and deepfake technologies further

complicates the attribution of creative labour and raises concerns about the erosion of performers' rights, especially in the absence of clear contractual standards or consent requirements.

Furthermore, insufficient safeguards against algorithmic bias threaten to perpetuate stereotypical representations and undermine cultural diversity in European cinema. This confluence of productivity incentives, regulatory gaps, copyright uncertainty, labour disparity and bias forms the central problem that this policy brief seeks to address.

Existing Policy Gap

Existing EU policy provides a general but fragmented foundation for AI in film. The already mentioned AI Act (Regulation 2024/1689) establishes a risk-based regime and obliges providers of generative-AI systems to disclose the copyrighted datasets used for training and to implement safeguards against unlawful content (European Parliament & Council of the European Union, 2024). However, the Act offers no sector-specific provisions for audiovisual creation, leaving safeguards for artistic integrity largely underdeveloped. In practice, the logging obligations outlined in Articles 12 and 19 apply only to high-risk systems and therefore exclude the generative AI tools most commonly used in filmmaking. Furthermore, Article 95 and Recital 165 limit traceability measures for low-risk systems to voluntary industry codes, leaving the provenance of creative outputs effectively unverifiable.

Data-privacy obligations are governed by the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR, 2016/679), which sets standards for lawful processing, consent and data minimisation that also apply to AI-driven media applications. Copyright protection is coordinated through the Copyright in the Digital Single Market Directive (DSM Directive, 2019/790), which introduces a text-and-data-mining (TDM) exception but primarily for scientific research; its commercial extension to AI training creates uncertainty for filmmakers (European Parliament, 2019; Han et al., 2012). The DSM Directive also reinforces the principle of human authorship, excluding purely machine-generated works from protection (Shrayberg & Volkova, 2021).

The DSM Directive requires rights-holders to “opt out” to prevent their works from being mined for AI training, putting a disproportionate weight of responsibility on individuals who already face a lot of the industry's labour malaise, such as precarity. Many audiovisual creators lack both the technical means and the legal awareness to implement these opt-outs effectively. As a result, vast amounts of European film and visual content may be incorporated into training datasets without explicit permission, complicating future copyright claims and attribution disputes. This status may be ‘legal’, but it is ethically questionable.

Cultural-policy instruments, such as Article 13 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights and the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), promote artistic freedom and cultural diversity, yet they, too, lack concrete mechanisms to address AI-generated content. The AVMSD provides no operational criteria for identifying, labelling or regulating AI-generated or AI-enhanced audiovisual content, creating uncertainty for broadcasters and streaming platforms as synthetic media becomes more prevalent. Emerging guidance on algorithmic bias highlights the need for transparency and fairness but remains vague for the film industry. Consequently, while a robust legal architecture exists for AI, its application to European cinema remains ambiguous, underscoring the urgency for film-specific guidelines and monitoring mechanisms.

Policy recommendations

This multifaceted landscape necessitates nuanced policy responses that carefully balance innovation, cultural preservation, equitable rights and social values, pointing to several policy implications forming the basis for the targeted recommendations that follow.

- **Human-protective policy by default** - Reverse policy guidelines and legal obligations toward human-centric principles that do not place humans as reactors to default technology acts. Provide the drivers seat to human and their organisations to determine the scope and frequency of use of works, whether copyrighted or orphan works. Assign the responsibility to AI systems by design to observe the law *and* ethical standards; design the 'giving back' obligation within these systems, by producing material for free for creators and for educational purposes at full capacity.
- **Transparency and data-set metadata** - EU AI-Act should move beyond high-level summaries to a standardised, machine-readable metadata framework and a centralised repository for granular tracking of training data. This could be implemented through an EU-level repository overseen by an independent supervisory authority, ensuring that filmmakers and rights-holders can verify whether their works have been used for model training.
- **Strengthening authorship rights** - Introduce enforceable hybrid-authorship categories that recognise human-AI collaboration and ensure fair attribution and remuneration, especially for smaller rights holders. Clarifying liability for outputs generated from copyrighted inputs would protect smaller creators, while hybrid-authorship rules would acknowledge human creative direction in AI-assisted works.
- **Ethical standards and certification** - Create binding, sector-specific ethical codes with mandatory bias-mitigation, inclusivity and transparent crediting, supported by a formal certification scheme akin to GDPR seals. A certification scheme could be integrated into

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Creative Europe or national film-funding mechanisms, making ethical compliance a prerequisite for public funding.

- **Fair remuneration and value sharing** - Establish a statutory licensing regime covering both AI-training inputs and commercialised outputs, with collective-management bodies handling continuous revenue sharing. This regime should include standardised reporting of AI-generated outputs and transparent revenue-tracking mechanisms to ensure fair contribution-based compensation.
- **Film-specific AI guidelines** - Develop specialised codes of practice that address AI use in scripting, VFX, casting and distribution, embedding risk-management, human oversight and cultural-diversity safeguards. These guidelines should include risk-assessment templates, documentation standards and explicit thresholds for acceptable levels of synthetic manipulation in narrative or documentary contexts.
- **Labour transition and upskilling** - Prioritise EU-funded programmes that boost digital literacy and creative-technology skills for film professionals adapting to AI-augmented workflows. Training should be embedded in national film schools and professional guilds, ensuring equitable access to new AI-related skills across the industry.
- **Funding for independents** - Provide dedicated financial mechanisms to help small filmmakers access AI tools responsibly, preventing market concentration by large corporations. Dedicated micro-grants or AI-infrastructure vouchers could support independent filmmakers who lack access to high-computational-cost tools.
- **Cultural safeguards and audits** - Strengthen Creative Europe and similar programmes to support pluralistic art forms and mandate regular independent audits of AI systems for representation, diversity and fairness. Independent audits should evaluate representational patterns in AI-generated content to safeguard against systemic bias and reinforce cultural diversity commitments.

Conclusion

As AI spreads quickly throughout Europe's film industry, it's revealing important gaps in regulation, questions of authorship, workers' rights, and the protection of cultural values. The EU has already built a solid legal framework with the AI Act, GDPR and the DSM Directive, but these tools are not yet applied in ways that properly address the needs of creative sectors. By developing film-specific guidelines, improving transparency and embedding ethical principles throughout every stage of production, Europe has the opportunity to become not just a rule-setter but a global leader in responsible, culturally aware and forward-thinking AI filmmaking. Above all, making sure that AI supports - rather than replaces human creativity will be essential for protecting artistic integrity,

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

cultural diversity and democratic values. This will require coordinated efforts from EU bodies, national governments and industry stakeholders to build a resilient, sustainable and competitive European film landscape in the AI era.

References

European Commission. (2020). *White paper on artificial intelligence—A European approach to excellence and trust*. European Commission. Retrieved from

https://commission.europa.eu/system/files/2020-02/commission-white-paper-artificial-intelligence-feb2020_en.pdf

European Commission. (2024). *Proposal for a regulation laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act)*. European Commission. Retrieved from [https://eur-](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401689)

[lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401689](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=OJ:L_202401689)

European Parliament, & Council of the European Union. (2019). *Directive (EU) 2019/790 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 April 2019 on copyright and related rights in the Digital Single Market and amending Directives 96/9/EC and 2001/29/EC (Text with EEA relevance)*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, L 130, 92–125. [https://eur-](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj)

[lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2019/790/oj)

European Parliament, & Council of the European Union. (2024). *Regulation (EU) 2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 laying down harmonised rules on artificial intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act)*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, 2024/1689.

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A32024R1689>

Ganuthula, V.R.R. (2025). AI-enabled individual entrepreneurship theory: redefining scale, capability, and sustainability in the digital age. *J Innov Entrep* 14, 85 .

<https://doi.org/10.1186/s13731-025-00521-9>

Han, J., Kamber, M., & Pei, J. (2012). *Data mining* (3rd ed.). Morgan Kaufmann.

Jiang, H. H., Brown, L., Cheng, J., Khan, M., Gupta, A., Workman, D., & Gebru, T. (2023, August). AI art and its impact on artists. In *Proceedings of the 2023 AAAI/ACM Conference on AI, Ethics, and Society* (pp. 363–374).

Khattak, M., Cohen, S. E., & Taylor, K. (2025). Who holds the camera? Filmmaking justice in the era of generative AI. *GRACE: Global Review of AI Community Ethics*, 3(1).

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Liu, J., Niu, Y., Jia, Z., & Wang, R. (2023). Assessing the ethical implications of artificial intelligence integration in media production and its impact on the creative industry. *MEDAAD*, 2023, 32–38.

Oberting IV, V. A. (2024). Generative artificial intelligence and copyright in the film and media industry. *Washington & Lee Law Review Online*, 82, 123.

Shrayberg, Y. L., & Volkova, K. Y. (2021). Features of copyright transformation in the information environment in the age of digitalization. *Scientific and Technical Information Processing*, 48(1), 30–37.

Thomas, S. (2024). AI and actors: Ethical challenges, cultural narratives and industry pathways in synthetic media performance. *Emerging Media*, 2(3), 523-546.

Yumeng, W., & Xiao, W. (2025). AI ethics in film industry: Two-way interaction and balance between technological innovation and humanistic care. *Frontiers in Art Research*, 7(3).

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Policy Brief

January 2026

Children's rights in the digital era: take-away policy recommendations for the film industry

Authors: Denise Amram, Jacopo Fortuna, Nicoletta Patti, Veronica Punzo, Roberta Romano (SSSA)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Introduction

According to the United Nations Convention on the Rights of the Child, in fact, the so-called principle of the best interest of the child shall be considered as a priority in all activities engaging minors (Bianca, 2021; Lamarque, 2016; Zermatten, 2020; Breen, 2002). In this regard, we took the challenge to verify the extent of existing provisions aiming to govern the digital dimension of the film services and products offer, in order to promote children's rights by addressing tailored interpretations of mechanisms, where children might be considered either as potential users or as actual ones (Nurhaqiqi - Kalaloi, 2025).

In the investigated film industry, indeed, children are both consumers and users of new (mainly digitalised) tools to enjoy products, offered through (or accompanied by) digital services, possibly including the support of systems based on artificial intelligence for several purposes: from the contents creation and delivery, to the marketing strategy (Fortuna, Patti, 2025). In this regard, the role of the comparative legal analysis focuses on addressing the principles stated within the EU Regulation 2016/679 on General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), the EU Regulation 2022/2065 on Digital Services Act (DSA) (Chander, 2023; Husovec, 2023), and the EU Regulation 2024/1689 on Artificial Intelligence (AIA) (Rebrean, Malgieri, 2024) with the lenses of Children's Rights, in order to contribute to define appropriate safeguards and set child-friendly boundaries to an everyday more digitalised audiovisual market.

The regulatory frameworks

The EU data strategy, indeed, is characterised by the allocation of roles and responsibilities towards institutional and private stakeholders aiming to define effective risk management and monitoring obligations that economic operators shall minimise to protect individuals or groups of individuals (Husovec, 2024; Thomaidou - Limniotis, 2025). As far as children are concerned, despite the mechanism of parental representation – that is the formal tool to protect minors within the contractual relationships - the digitalisation of services and products arises a series of risks of exposure to harms that shall be prevented by design and by default (Livingstone, Stoilova, 2021). In particular, within the marketing strategies, the profiling and targeted advertising, the collection of behavioural data, the generation of psychometric profiles, and the use of predictive techniques are daily attempting consumers' autonomy and privacy (Leijten, Van der Hof, 2024). They can therefore undermine also cognitive, emotional, and moral development, especially in a child, whose capacity of discernment is strongly limited, and a distortive perception could have implications not only on the given service and product provision, but also in their growth and education (Clemente-Suárez *et al.*, 2024). The same risks might emerge in case of exposure to harmful or inappropriate contents: they may strongly

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

affect the child's opinions and values (OECD, 2025). Another ground of analysis concerns the role of cultural industries to foster unprecedented opportunities of capacity building, that current young users shall (and must) take through the acquisition of unprecedented skills and competence offered by the access and variety of contents in film industry (Sanjuán, 2025). To this end, a child-friendly film industry shall be the one whose strategies are suitable to combine the challenge to properly balance the need to prevent and mitigate risks for children and, at the same time, to boost the opportunities of growth by ensuring equal access to resources that are considered safe, inclusive, and appropriate to the maturity of the given user, considered not as a merely consumer, but as a rights-holder and cultural participant, as well¹.

The recalled EU regulatory framework has progressively introduced obligations for economic operators to assess, prevent, and mitigate the mentioned risks for general users. However, only few provisions are specifically addressed to protect children as a group of vulnerable users (Malgieri, 2022) of the current data economy. As a consequence, economic operators are called to directly and case-by-case introduce tailored safeguards for children. In this regard, a systematic collection of the technical standards, organisational safeguards, and best practices adopted by private and public stakeholders for each mentioned normative framework could be interpreted in the context of the European film industry to contribute to design the legal premises for a child-friendly one.

For instance, the GDPR sets clear boundaries on data processing activities, despite the economic sector where the data controller operates. In particular, it prohibits automated decision-making producing legal or similarly significant effects (Art. 22) and it calls for heightened protections when processing the data of children (Recital 38), considering that, according to article 8 GDPR, the threshold to express a valid consent to process personal data in the digital dimension is reduced at 16 years old, even allowing Member States to set a lower age. Within the national enforcement experiences, a good practice is represented by the UK's Children's Code, strongly attentive to children's rights and compatible with the EU data protection laws also after Brexit, requiring that profiling activities shall be avoided by default unless demonstrably adopted in the child's best interest. The reversal of the burden of proof is aligned with the technical safeguards aiming to introduce age-appropriate transparency features, including data minimisation, and responsible interface design both for parents and children (S. Rigazio, 2024; J. Mootz, K. Blocker, et al., 2024; N. Patti, V. Punzo, R. Romano, 2025). The DSA expressly strengthens the protection for children

¹ See Sanjuán (2025), who conceptualises cultural and creative industries as key enablers of individual and collective wellbeing when access to cultural resources is framed in terms of participation, capability development and inclusion rather than mere consumption. The author stresses that the positive impact of cultural industries—especially for young people—depends on the availability of safe, age-appropriate and inclusive cultural environments, as well as on policy and industry strategies capable of balancing risk mitigation with the promotion of cultural participation and personal development.

(Fortuna, 2025), by explicitly requiring a tailored assessment of risks for this category of users and by banning targeted advertising based on profiling when it concerns minors (Article 28). However, this prohibition applies only to services that qualify as online platforms under the DSA, including social platforms, which allow content sharing and interactions also of film contents. Conversely, video-on-demand services that do not host user-generated content or facilitate user interaction are not subjected to these due diligence obligations by the economic operators. In this regard, the EU Directive n. 2010/13 on Audiovisual Media Services Directive (hereinafter “AVMSD”), that introduced the principle of digital and media literacy as a key element to empower citizens’ rights to make informed decisions, detect disinformation, and actively participate in contemporary society also within the audio-visual and media economic sectors (Ranaivoson, Broughton Micova, Raats, 2023) is currently under assessment on the premises that “*there is uneven protection of viewers, in particular minors, across different distribution platforms*”². AIA indeed is looking at children’s rights protection in order to avoid that “*powerful tools for manipulative, exploitative and social control practices*” could be developed, placed into the market and generate a manipulative effect or “an adverse impact” on children as vulnerable users (Recital 28, Article 9).

Despite these regulatory advances, profiling practices prevail in practice. Children are often unknowingly subject to behavioural tracking, algorithmic personalisation, and cross-platform data aggregation—techniques that are largely invisible and incomprehensible to adults and, therefore, even less by younger users. These systems exploit minors’ developmental vulnerabilities, exposing them to commercial pressures and conditioning their digital behaviour (Hilbert *et al.*, 2025). In this regard, technical standards and compliance requirements for economic operators do not appear sufficient to protect children’s rights.

Enhancing Children’s rights: barriers and enablers.

A systemic approach that goes beyond the traditional dichotomy between parental responsibility and platform autonomy is therefore required. A coordinated effort is needed between the regulators, the media, the technology industries, the civil society, and the educational institutions to establish shared standards, promote digital-media literacy, and encourage design models that could respect children not only as users, but as rights holders and participants in cultural life. Only by combining these layers children could be respected not merely as consumers, but as persons within a

² DG-CNET, Audiovisual Media Services Directive – evaluation and review, Ref. Ares(2025)10181999 - 23/11/2025, considering the report by K. Attström, V. Ludden, A. Iliescu, *Survey and data gathering to support the impact assessment of a possible new legislative proposal concerning directive 2010/13/eu (avmsd) and in particular the provisions on the protection of minors*, 2015, https://ec.europa.eu/newsroom/dae/document.cfm?action=display&doc_id=15876 and the technological development faced in the last years.

community of users of – for instance - platforms that are playing a pivotal contribution in shaping society’s news, information, and entertainment agenda. One suggested strategy for addressing the impacts of platformization (Helmond, 2015) on children is to promote their cultural rights by ensuring access to a wide range of cultural content, protecting them from harmful materials, enhancing media and digital literacy, and fostering their participation in cultural activities.

In this regard, we need to explore the role of adults, like parents, relatives and educators, as it remains essential to avoid the exposure of minors to harmful contents (Senigaglia, 2021b). In addition, the approach shall be oriented not only to protect the vulnerable users, but also allow them to be enriched by the film experience in terms of cultural growth and opportunities to develop own opinions and tastes, to better understand current society, and to develop the proper skills to actively participate to the current societal challenges. If children are allowed to be active parties in the decision-making process, bringing their perspectives and participation as valuable contribution to that cultural industry, then it would be easier to address their needs and attitudes as users. Integrating high-quality audiovisual content can therefore improve children's educational experiences by encouraging creativity and critical thinking (Fortuna, Patti, 2025).

From a technical viewpoint, the most common solution adopted as a result of the balance to protect and promote children’s rights as users of digital services and products, including those related to film industry is to introduced parental controls as a firewall to get access or select contents available to the given user. This is widely recognised as a first-line safeguard for children’s access to digital audiovisual content as well. Yet, its effectiveness is often constrained by two structural factors, like the opaque design choices on the part of platforms — from persuasive interfaces to data-driven recommendation systems that may manipulate users’ behaviours — and uneven digital literacy at home, which can limit parents’ ability to configure and supervise the available tools as well as to address the challenge to develop a critical thinking on the proposed contents (Mauk, 2021)³.

Indeed, parents are often left without sufficient resources to make informed decisions or effectively guide their children's digital experiences. It is therefore essential to support parents not only through technological tools, but also through education and awareness campaigns on the implications emerging from the datafication of services and products (Battelli, 2021). Parental controls, in fact, should not be seen as a substitute for parental engagement, but as an enabler of more extended exercise of parental responsibilities. Children benefit most when technical protections are coupled with active co-viewing, critical discussion, and clear household norms. Promoting a critical approach

³ A baseline set of parental-control features, such as age-rating filters, profile PINs, title blocking, watch-time limits, and dedicated “Kids” interfaces are offered by the most common platforms, however, these controls are rarely enabled by default, differ markedly from service to service, and seldom explain how recommendation algorithms and content classifications actually work.

to digital media, from shared viewing practices to open discussions about online content, can improve children's ability to navigate the digital landscape with autonomy and awareness⁴ shall go beyond passive content decoding and encourage autonomous and conscious production, critical thinking, and subjectivity. These goals can only be met through multilevel governance and co-design with schools, public authorities, the media industry, and the civil society (Fortuna, Patti, 2025).

Towards a child-friendly competitive film industry: take-away policies.

A child-friendly and competitive film industry therefore requires not only protection mechanisms but also the active promotion of children's cultural rights, in line with Article 31 of the UNCRC and Article 12 of the EU Charter of Fundamental Rights. To achieve this goal, regulation and policy must move beyond prohibitive measures and embrace a positive agenda, fostering access, awareness, and meaningful participation. Under these premises, the following take-away policy and recommendations can be addressed either to policy makers, or to the economic operators of the film industry, or to families to better promote a child-friendly, inclusive, safer digital environment to enjoy the given cultural experience in the current ages.

First of all, in order to mitigate these risks and ensure meaningful protection for children, the following regulatory and design strategies are recommended to be implemented either in possible legal instruments aiming to align the audiovisual market to the application of new technologies or to soft law instruments that could be developed as guidelines to undertake the obligations of risks assessments.

- **High-privacy settings by default:** Platforms should deactivate profiling and behavioural tracking for underage users by default, requiring explicit parental consent for any activation.
- **Age-appropriate transparency measures:** This technical recommendation aims both to introduce layered limits to the content access and to raise awareness on the consequences of data processing activities enabled in the use of digital services and products. Therefore, privacy information must be also tailored to the cognitive maturity of the end-users even though represented by their parents. In a progressive way, then, in case of children suitable to directly express own consent for data processing activities and use of AI-based systems, understandable and plain language, icons, and layered explanations shall be provided.
- **Non-personalised recommendation options:** Platforms should offer content-access modes that do not rely on behavioural profiling, allowing minors to explore cultural content free from commercial targeting. This is also aligned with the ban on dark patterns. In fact,

⁴ The European Parliament recommendations on key competences for lifelong learning define digital competence as the ability to use technologies in a critical, confident, and creative manner, integrating it with civic and social competence, see EU Parliament recommendations n. 2006/962/EC and n. 2018/C 189/01.

any interface design that nudges, pressures, or misleads children into sharing data or accepting personalised advertising must be prohibited under article 25 DSA. This applies especially to exploitative tactics like autoplay, fake countdowns, and ambiguous consent buttons.

These recommendations shall be supported by a mechanism of monitoring, auditing that could oversight the process in light of children's rights. In this regard, we would suggest to:

- **Tailor monitoring and auditing mechanisms to children's needs, attitudes, and rights.** In this regard, to scrutinise how algorithms work, to identify harmful practices, considering the principle of the best interest of the child in the given scenario, specific competence and expertise shall be required for auditors, competent officers, etc. in order to provide proper advices and enforce the compliance of economic operators and address it towards the needs of that specific category of vulnerable users. To protect children from profiling and targeted advertising requires, indeed, a shift from solely consent to prevention by design and by default. Children's rights must be embedded at the structural level, through fairness-by-design and privacy-by-default approaches, that shall limit data exploitation and promote child autonomy as a priority. Advertising —particularly in hybrid entertainment environments— must be regulated not only as commerce, but as a powerful vector of influence, warranting clear, proportionate, and enforceable safeguards whenever children are involved.
- **Make parental controls substantively child centred.** From a technical viewpoint, this means that child accounts shall: i) embed an opt-in rather than an opt-out model; ii) include clear, accessible, and age-appropriate interfaces, with visual cues and plain-language prompts; age-classification criteria shall be transparent and offer insights into the factors that drive personalised recommendations; granular filtering —age brackets, thematic categories, explicit-content flags— shall be enabled and parents shall be able to allow to lock or disable autoplay; monitoring dashboards (usage time, viewing history, flagging of sensitive content) and easy-to-use reporting tools shall be embedded; co-viewing and dialogue, e.g. shared watch-lists, content summaries, and parental guidance notes that prompt discussion shall be encouraged also through alerts and warnings.
- **Reinforce the cooperation between the film industry and education.** Ensuring and facilitating minors' access to an educational and high-quality audiovisual panorama is critical for revitalising modern education and acting as a bridge between training practices and new communication languages. Educational institutions play a crucial role in introducing young people to diverse cinematic languages, promoting critical viewing, and bridging the gap between entertainment and cultural literacy. Partnerships with streaming platforms and film

industry stakeholders can facilitate curated access to high-quality content, including European and independent productions, and promote educational initiatives such as school-based film clubs, platform-integrated didactic materials, and thematic film festivals. The cultural industry can help by developing educational content that is both informative and entertaining while also educating, especially to the challenges launched by the digital environment. Documentaries, films, animated series, and interactive programmes can all be used to teach complex concepts in a simple and engaging manner, stimulating children's curiosity and imagination. This content can be distributed via digital platforms and used in schools to supplement the educational curriculum. To be guided by educators in the access to digital services and products may build specific capabilities and raise awareness also in terms of digital literacy. Effective collaborations between schools, platforms, and the cultural industry can create and nurture a genuine educational ecosystem in which children (*rectius* students) can interact with high-quality content, engage in creative activities, and develop social and cognitive abilities.

The policy and recommendations addressed in this short contribution are converging on the need to promote awareness, literacy for children in the digital age, including the audiovisual and media environment. Inclusive, cultural and educational contexts may in fact guarantee that children could be protected in their access to resources but also that they can play an active role as users and consumers of the given film industry in EU⁵. At the same time, it is critical to ensure that educational and digital environments are accessible and usable to everyone, regardless of physical or cognitive abilities, language, or cultural background. Initiatives such as the European Parliament's resolution on media literacy in a digital world (2008/2129(INI)) advocate for a fair and supportive model in which access to technology and digital culture is recognised as a collective right. Overcoming the digital divide, both infrastructural and cultural, requires the implementation of local strategies tailored to the needs of communities, with a focus on disadvantaged groups. In this framework, children's active participation has both pedagogical and political implications.

As stated, Article 12 and Article 31 of the UNCRC provide the foundation a virtuous model, which integrates access, participation, and expression as core educational principles. Embedding children's rights into the design and delivery of cultural policies and educational programmes fosters both agency and equity. Empowering children and adolescents to critically navigate audiovisual content, recognise manipulative techniques (such as dark patterns or algorithmic biases), and

⁵ Media education and media literacy, as a result of this educational process, have been described and defined in an international context by UNESCO, in an initiative that began in 1982 with the conference in Grunwald (1982), and continued with conferences in Toulouse (1990), Vienna (1999), and Seville (2002), documents that highlight how media education must be an integral part of formal and informal education and represents a critical element for democratic participation.

understand the economic and narrative structures behind digital platforms is essential. Media literacy must be therefore integrated into national education systems with age-appropriate curricula, in cooperation with civil society organisations and the media sector.

References

- Amram, D. (2022). *Children (in the Digital Environment)*. In G. Comandé (eds.), *Elgar Encyclopedia of Law and Data Science*, 2022, p. 64 ff.
- Amram, D. (2024). *Standards to Face Children and Patients Digital Vulnerabilities*. In C. Crea - A. De Franceschi (eds.), *The New Shapes of Digital Vulnerability in European Private Law*, 2024, p. 439 ff.
- Battelli, E. (2021). *Minori e social network: Cyberbullismo e limiti della parental responsibility*, *Il Corriere Giuridico*, 38(9), 1269-1277.
- Bianca, M. (2021) (ed), *The best interest of the child*, Roma.
- Breen, C. (2002). *The standard of the best interests of the child: A Western tradition, International and Comparative Law*, The Hague.
- Chander, A. (2023), *When the Digital Services Act Goes Global*, *Berkeley Technology Law Journal*, 38, p. 1067 ff.
- Clemente-Suárez, V. J., Beltrán-Velasco, A. I., Herrero-Roldán, S., Rodríguez-Besteiro, S., Martínez-Guardado, I., Martín-Rodríguez, A., & Tornero-Aguilera, J. F. (2024). Digital device usage and childhood cognitive development: Exploring effects on cognitive abilities. *Children*, 11(11), 1299.
- Fortuna, J. (2025). *Minors' Digital Vulnerability in the EU and the US: A Comparison Between The Digital Services Act and The Kids Online Safety and Privacy Act*, *Comparative Law Review*, 16, 2025, p.115 ff.
- Fortuna, J., Patti, N. (2025). Children's rights and the cinematic experience in the digital age: Addressing regulatory challenges. *Opinio Juris in Comparatione*, 2.
- Helmond, A. (2015). The platformization of the web: Making web data platform ready. *Social Media + Society*, 1(2), 2056305115603080.

Hilbert, M., Cingel, D. P., Zhang, J., Vigil, S. L., Shawcroft, J., Xue, H., ... & Shafiq, Z. (2025). #BigTech@ Minors: social media algorithms have actionable knowledge about child users and at-risk teens. *Telematics and Informatics*, 102341.

Husovec, M. (2024). *Principles of the Digital Services Act*, Oxford.

Husovec, M. (2024). The Digital Services Act's red line: What the Commission can and cannot do about disinformation. *Journal of Media Law*, 16(1), 1-20.

J. Zermatten, *The Best Interests of the Child Principle: Literal Analysis and Function*, *The International Journal of Children's Rights*, 18(4), 2020, pp. 483–499.

Jänterä-Jareborg, Maarit (2016), *The Child's Interests in Conflict*, Larcier.

Lamarque, E. (2016). *Prima i bambini. Il principio dei best interests of the child nella prospettiva costituzionale*. FrancoAngeli.

Lamarque, E. (2023). Pesare le parole. Il principio dei best interests of the child come principio del miglior interesse del minore, *Famiglia e dir.*, 4, p. 365 ff.

Leijten, E., van der Hof, S. (2024). Dissecting the commercial profiling of children: A proposed taxonomy and assessment of the GDPR, DSA and AI Act in light of the precautionary principle. SSRN. <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5055046>.

Livingstone, S. Stoilova, M., *The 4Cs: Classifying Online Risk to Children*, *CO:RE Short Report Series on Key Topics*, Hamburg: Leibniz-Institut für Medienforschung | Hans-Bredow-Institut (HBI), CO:RE - Children Online: Research and Evidence, 2021.

Malgieri, G. (2022). *Vulnerability*, in G. Comandé (eds.), *Elgar Encyclopedia of Law and Data Science*, 2022, p. 363 ff.

Mauk, M. (2021), *Think of the Parents: Parental Controls in Digital TV and Family Implications*, in Holloway, D., Willson, M., Murcia, K., Archer, C., Stocco, F. (eds) *Young Children's Rights in a Digital World. Children's Well-Being: Indicators and Research*, vol 23, pp. 81 – 92, 2021.

Mootz, J., Blocker, K., et al. (2024). *UK age-appropriate design code: Impact assessment*. Institute for Digital Media and Child Development / Children & Screens.

<https://www.childrenandscreens.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/03/Children-and-Screens-UK-AADC-Impact-Assessment.pdf>.

Nurhaqiqi, H., & Kalaloi, A. F. (2025). Concern on media regulation and children's rights: A bibliometric study. *SAGE Open*, 15(3).

OECD. (2025). *How's life for children in the digital age?* OECD Publishing.

Patti, N., Punzo, V., & Romano, R. (2025). *Child vulnerabilities in the digital environment: Comparative insights and operational guidelines*, *Opinio Juris in Comparatione*, 2.

Ranaivoson, H., Broughton Micova, S., Raats, T. (Eds.). (2023). *European audiovisual policy in transition*. Routledge.

Rebrean, M.-L., & Malgieri, G. (2025). *Vulnerability in the EU AI Act: Building an interpretation*, in *Proceedings of the 2025 ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAccT '25)* (pp. 1985–1997). <https://doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.5058591>.

Rigazio, S. (2024). *L'empowerment del minore nella dimensione digitale*, Mucchi Editore.

Sanjuán, J. (2025). *How do cultural and creative industries shape wellbeing? A multidisciplinary review*. *European Journal of Cultural Management and Policy*, 15, 14774.

Scarano L. A. (2021). The best interest of the child nella giurisprudenza della Corte suprema di Cassazione. In M. Bianca (a cura di), *The best interest of the child*, Roma, p. 101 ff.

Senigaglia R. (2021). The best interest of the child tra persona e contratto. In M. Bianca (a cura di), *The best interest of the child*, Roma, p. 491 ff.

Senigaglia, R. (2021). Il dovere di educare i figli nell'era digitale. *Persona e Mercato*, 3(3), 511-525.

Thomaidou, A., & Limniotis, K. (2025). Navigating through human rights in AI: Exploring the interplay between GDPR and fundamental rights impact assessment. *Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy*, 5(1), 7.

Policy Brief

January 2026

Streaming services and the competitiveness of the European Film Industry in Europe and Latin America

Authors: Marina Rossato Fernandes, Antonios Vlassis (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Mafalda Dâmaso (EUR)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Context

Streaming services, including VOD (i.e. Netflix, Prime Video) and video-sharing service providers (i.e. YouTube), have become key gatekeepers in the international circulation of audiovisual content, reshaping how films are produced, distributed, and consumed. Their rapid expansion poses significant governance challenges for European policy-makers, particularly regarding the competitiveness of the European Film Industry (EFI) and the achievement of EU cultural and industrial policy objectives.

Recent research shows that US-based VOD service providers, such as Netflix, Amazon and Disney, are reshaping national production cultures, funding models, and content circulation, with significant implications for the visibility of European works (Idiz, 2024; lordache et al., 2022). Indeed, VOD services play a decisive role in determining the availability and discoverability of films, with certain titles receiving greater prominence than others (Lobato & Scarlata, 2022; Smits, 2022). Notwithstanding the fact that European films featured on these VOD services are predominantly from major production countries (namely the UK, France, Spain, Italy, and Germany), issues of visibility, prominence and discoverability have become central to recommending films to audiences and facilitating their circulation. As Albornoz and Gallo (2024) note, VOD services determine not only which content is available, but also when and to whom. In this context, prominence and visibility have emerged as critical bottlenecks in contemporary film circulation.

Scholarship reveals that streaming services are transforming power relations across the production, distribution, and exhibition sectors. In other words, streaming services have created opportunities to potentially challenge the long-standing dominance of traditional Hollywood studios (Vlassis 2021a, Smits, 2024), where the release patterns of film, involving multiple exploitation windows, beginning with theatrical, home video (e.g. DVDs), pay-TV and broadcast has collapsed (Ulin, 2019; Chalaby, 2025).

Beyond the impact on the circulation of European content, the model applied by US VOD services when commissioning audiovisual works from local companies has altered the financing and production landscape. In particular, US VOD services typically demand all-encompassing rights, across formats and territories, which results in a de facto full transfer of intellectual property (IP) (Meir & Mitric, 2025; Chalaby, 2023; Doyle et al., 2021) that limits local producers' ability to profit from their own back catalogues or build long-term value.

The growing influence of these streaming services is transforming established industry practices and putting existing regulatory frameworks under pressure (García Leiva & Albornoz, 2020; Chalaby, 2025). While scholarly interest in the topic is growing, there remains a lack of empirical evidence on how film professionals experience and perceive the influence of predominantly US-based streamers. As the EU revises and implements the Audiovisual Media Services Directive (AVMSD), understanding the perspectives of European film professionals becomes crucial (Vlassis 2023, García Leiva, 2025). Equally important are the perceptions of non-European professionals, which shed light on how European cinema is received and circulated beyond the EU.

Indeed, reinforcing the role of the EU as a global actor in a sustainable manner requires ensuring that the views and the needs of non-European actors are understood and taken into account in policymaking. Such a stance can be described as a decentering EU film policy . Simultaneously, it is necessary to contribute in an evidence-based manner to current debates regarding the EU's global audiovisual policy. The EU has long positioned itself as a global normative actor in the cultural field (Dâmaso, 2025) and this approach was reinforced with the adoption of the 2005 UNESCO Convention on the Protection and Promotion of the Diversity of Cultural Expressions, through which the EU seeks to embed cultural norms and audiovisual cooperation within broader economic and political frameworks (Vlassis, 2021b). Among non-European markets, Latin America emerges as a particularly significant case. It has long been a key destination for European films and has often paid attention to European audiovisual policy models when shaping its own frameworks (Vlassis 2016, Fernandes, 2023). Yet, VOD services in the region remain largely unregulated, raising important concerns about access, visibility, and policy leverage in the global media landscape . At the same time, the EU's earlier normative influence in regional policy debates diminished (Fernandes, 2022), as global VOD services increasingly shape regulatory agendas across Latin America (Fernandes & Albornoz, 2023). Current debates in Brazil over the regulation of streaming services illustrate these tensions. The independent production sector has been pushing for an ambitious regulatory framework, and this position has received explicit support from European independent production associations. The European Producers Club and the European Audiovisual Production Association publicly endorsed the efforts of Brazilian independent producers to advance a balanced and effective regulatory model for streaming services (European Producers Club & CEPI, 2024). At the same time, the growing influence of global streaming platforms in the policy process has raised concerns, with industry stakeholders noting that these services are exerting increasing pressure to shape the proposed legislation.

To explore these dynamics, this policy brief combines qualitative and quantitative data collected by ULIEGE, EUR, and IUCE-UC3M in two REBOOT tasks: 4.1 focused on European film professionals

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

(Fernandes et al. 2025), and 4.3, on non-European professionals (Dâmaso et al, 2025). The data includes 37 interviews with European film professionals and a pan-European survey of over 400 respondents, with 47 interviews with Latin American film professionals and a survey of over 197 respondents in the three biggest markets in Latin America, Argentina, Brazil, and México. In doing so, it offers evidence-based recommendations to strengthen the long-term competitiveness of the EFI in the evolving VOD landscape. Particular attention is given to the tensions and conflicts that arise when European and non-European film professionals engage with global VOD services, how EU policy can respond to these dynamics to support a more competitive and resilient film sector, and what this implies for future cultural and policy exchanges between the regions.

Discussion

The findings revealed that film professionals view VOD service providers as central yet problematic actors in the contemporary audiovisual landscape. While non-EU film professionals highlighted the role of streaming services, particularly MUBI and Netflix, in supporting the global circulation of European films, EFI professionals emphasised that, despite this increased reach, the know-how and infrastructure continue to be concentrated within US-based global players. Moreover, respondents agree that releasing films in cinemas continues to be an important strategy to support the dissemination of European film. While VOD opened up new opportunities to reach audiences, when asked about the main obstacles to the international distribution of European film, all case studies identified competition from Hollywood productions. That is, despite the opportunities created by streaming services to transform power relations, Hollywood players have tended to dominate even in this new market.

In the European context, while recognising the role of VOD services in expanding access to European content, participants highlighted several interconnected challenges affecting the EFI's competitiveness. A central concern is the concentration of market power in US-based companies, which increasingly set the terms of collaboration and limit the creative and contractual autonomy of European producers. Interviewees described a widening gap in bargaining power, noting that negotiations with VOD services often lack transparency and leave producers with little room to negotiate favourable conditions or retain control over their works.

The findings show that the benefits of VOD services in Europe are uneven across countries, markets, professions, and segments of the value chain, with directors, distributors, the animation sector and professionals in smaller or lower-capacity markets benefiting far less. Respondents also highlighted that the current environment tends to weaken SMEs, which face growing difficulties in maintaining visibility, securing fair deals, and sustaining independent production.

These challenges are intensified by the lack of transparency, particularly regarding how VOD services collect and use audience data and how they recommend content. Professionals reported that this opacity prevents producers and public institutions from understanding the performance of European works and from making informed decisions. They are further compounded by the limited discoverability of European content on VOD services and the increasing dependence on US-based private companies that are not structurally committed to the long-term development of the EFI. Professionals argue that these VOD service providers profit from the creative talent, production capacity and infrastructure built over decades through European public investment, yet do not sufficiently reinvest in the sector or contribute to its structural development. As a result, concerns emerge regarding the long-term sustainability of EFI, the preservation of cultural diversity, and Europe's capacity to retain control over its cultural assets.

In Latin America, the introduction of VOD services has been seen as an opportunity to showcase certain productions that otherwise would not have a window of exhibition, but it has also brought its own set of challenges. For local distributors, VOD services have reduced revenue that could be generated by films, bypassing local intermediaries, preferring instead to secure global or at least regional rights directly from international sales agents. It has also contributed to the marginalisation of physical media formats, such as DVDs and Blu-rays, heightening the financial risks for independent film distributors, particularly given the limited promotional resources available to these smaller actors, making profitability difficult.

Regarding production, US-based global VOD service providers' investments and guaranteed international work distribution have expanded creative and funding opportunities, challenging the long-standing dominance of legacy broadcasters and theatrical circuits. However, it has also increased concerns among local producers when it comes to retaining IP rights and prompted discussions among film professionals regarding its regulation, particularly concerning quotas for domestic content, similar to the EU model.

When asked about the challenges faced by their local markets, Argentinian interviewees highlighted the need to regulate streaming services as a key concern. Despite acknowledging that the arrival of US-based VOD services expanded private investment opportunities and broadened the audience for local productions, interviewees also foregrounded their introduction of a new set of challenges around IP rights and creative control of the works. Similarly, many of the same challenges encountered in the Argentinian case are also present in Brazil, such as a lack of exhibition space for independent films (including European) and the need for better support for distribution and promotion. The need to regulate streaming services was also among the most frequently cited challenges by film professionals in Argentina and Brazil. As per Mexico, several recurrent challenges

shape the current landscape of its film industry. While also acknowledging the widespread dominance of Hollywood at the box office, most interviewees pointed to deeper structural issues in terms of distribution, promotion, and exhibition. Particularly, some participants highlighted the urgent need for an independent exhibition circuit.

Overall, the study shows strong support among professionals for reinforcing and expanding regulation on streaming services, whether in the EU or Latin America. Building on these insights, the policy recommendations outlined below identify areas where coordinated action at the European level could strengthen the EFI's competitiveness. They reflect professionals' calls for more robust VOD regulation, ensuring that creative freedom and cultural diversity remain central to the EFI.

Policy Recommendations

Support EFI competitiveness

- **Reinforce control over Intellectual Property (IP) (long-term)**

Rationale: The findings show that professionals across the EFI perceive loss of IP control as one of the most critical threats to long-term competitiveness. Interviewees consistently described how global VOD service providers acquire exclusive rights, often preventing European producers from monetising further or re-exploiting their own works. These arrangements often resemble “work-for-hire” contracts rather than genuine co-productions, meaning that public investment and European talent contribute to global content portfolios without generating lasting assets for the EFI. Strengthening IP control is therefore essential for securing sustainable business models and ensuring that European audiovisual content remains a source of cultural and economic value within Europe.

Recommendation: Introduce stronger safeguards ensuring that European producers and creators retain ownership of intellectual property. This may include linking public funding and VOD investment obligations to IP retention, restricting exclusive buy-out practices, and promoting contract standards that guarantee European control over exploitation rights and future revenues.

- **Increase support for the independent audiovisual sector (medium-term)**

Rationale: According to European professionals, SMEs across the EFI face limited negotiation power and reduced creative control when working with global VOD service providers. These players follow business models that differ from the European ecosystem and often constrain producers' autonomy. Professionals warned that budget inflation and VOD commissioning are creating a divide within the EFI between high-budget, VOD-oriented productions and smaller independent works that struggle to compete. They also expressed

concern about the sector's growing dependency on US-based companies, which profit from European talent and infrastructures developed through public investment but remain uncommitted to the EFI's long-term sustainability.

Recommendation: Reinforce public support for SMEs and independent producers to counterbalance the dominance of US-based VOD service providers. Dedicate part of VOD investment obligations or levies to dedicated funds designed to support all segments of the audiovisual sector, extending beyond production.

- **Strengthening regulation towards streaming services (medium-term)**

Rationale: Film professionals demonstrate broad and consistent support for strong regulation towards streaming platforms, including VOD services and video-sharing platforms, and explicit recognition of the AVMSD's importance as a policy instrument. Professionals identify quotas and investment obligations as essential for guaranteeing the presence of European works, particularly in small-language and low-capacity markets. Professionals emphasised that the current framework does not adequately address imbalances across EU countries, sectors, and stages of the value chain. The findings highlight that VOD benefits tend to concentrate in a few countries and production-heavy segments, while sectors such as distribution and animation receive limited support.

Recommendation: Strengthen the AVMSD by refining and expanding its existing mechanisms. Introduce sub-quotas for animation, promote harmonisation of investment obligations across member states, and establish targeted measures that ensure regulatory benefits extend to the entire audiovisual value chain, including distributors and other underrepresented sectors. Such adjustments would enhance the Directive's effectiveness, reduce internal asymmetries, and ensure that regulation towards streaming providers, including VOD services and video-sharing platforms, contributes meaningfully to the sustainability and competitiveness of the EFI as a whole.

Transparency and Pominence

- **Promote Data Transparency and Algorithmic Accountability in Operations of Streaming Services (medium-term)**

Rationale: The findings highlight that limited access to viewership and algorithmic data from global streaming service providers poses a major challenge for the EFI. Without reliable data, producers and public agencies cannot accurately assess the audience reach and impact of European works. This undermines evidence-based policymaking and weakens the capacity of European institutions to evaluate and adjust existing measures. The opacity of data practices also creates structural imbalances in the sector: while other audiovisual players

are obliged to report performance data, global streaming service providers are not. As a result, European producers lack crucial knowledge about how their content performs, information essential for improving future production, marketing, and investment strategies.

Recommendation: Establish EU-wide obligations for streaming service providers, including VOD services and video-sharing platforms, to share audience, performance, and algorithmic data on European productions. Require transparency regarding how recommendation systems rank European works, and implement auditing mechanisms.

- **Provide a clear definition and enforcement of prominence (medium-term)**

Rationale: Respondents stressed that inclusion in VOD catalogues is not sufficient if European content remains difficult to find, poorly ranked, or overshadowed by promotional strategies. A well-defined and enforceable concept of prominence is therefore essential to ensure that European works are not merely present but effectively visible within the digital environment. Professionals also emphasised the need for accurate and consistent attribution of production companies.

Recommendation: Provide a clear definition of the prominence of European works and introduce mandatory discoverability rules for European content on streaming services, including VOD platforms and video-sharing providers, and mechanisms to monitor it. Ensure transparent and consistent attribution of European production companies in all European works available on these services.

International cooperation

- **Strengthen initiatives to support digital distribution in international markets (medium-term)**

Rationale: Latin American industry stakeholders indicate that the exhibitor and distributor sector is highly concentrated in all three Latin American countries studied and while European films are present in streaming services, the majority of the films that reach these services are from the main producing countries: United Kingdom, France, Spain, Italy, and Germany. Although there are existing support programs from certain countries to support the circulation of their own films, these programs do not focus on digital distribution.

Recommendation: Considering the difficulties outlined by interviewees, the EU should consider establishing an overarching program to support the international distribution of European films that includes support for distribution through digital outlets. This would give films from smaller countries, which currently lack distribution support programs, a better chance to reach international audiences while simultaneously broadening the reach of films from countries that provide distribution support beyond theatrical exhibition

- **Leverage partnerships with streaming services (short-term)**

Rationale: The Latin American market for streaming services is strong and growing, and US-based global VOD service providers maintain a dominant position in the VOD sector. Additionally, the majority of the content offered in these services originates from the United States.

Recommendation: Given the growing importance of VOD services in the international circulation of films and the fact that Latin America has an avid consumer base for these services, it could be interesting to leverage partnerships with public VOD services such as CineAR Play (Argentina) or Nuestro Cine MX (Mexico) to facilitate the exchange of audiovisual content, providing an additional exhibition window for European films while potentially creating opportunities for Latin American productions within the EU market. In addition, a targeted program for local or regional VOD services with a focus on niche and curated cinema, interested in acquiring and showcasing European films in non-EU markets after their theatrical release should be considered. The program could offer financial incentives, rights-clearing assistance, support with dubbing or subtitling, or even curated catalogues to make European films more easily accessible.

- **Promote EU–Latin America dialogue on VOD regulation (short-term)**

Rationale: Latin America remains an important market for European works, yet streaming services, including VOD providers and video-sharing platforms in the region, operate with limited regulatory oversight. The study indicates that Latin American professionals broadly support regulation towards streaming services and share challenges similar to their European counterparts regarding visibility and the sustainability of independent production. At the same time, the EU's previous normative influence in regional audiovisual policy debates is weakening, as global VOD services increasingly shape regulatory agendas.

Recommendation: Promote structured dialogue and cooperation between the EU and Latin America on regulatory approaches to streaming services. Encourage exchanges among film professionals, associations, regulatory bodies, and public institutions to debate policy options, share experiences, and discuss regulatory practices.

- **Update co-production agreements (long-term)**

Rationale: Latin American film professionals highlighted the importance of co-production agreements between Latin American and European countries not only to pool financial, technical, and creative resources, but also to potentially increase access to audiences and opportunities for festival circulation. Coproductions also benefit from policy instruments that foster the exhibition of domestic films across both regions.

Recommendation: Update coproductions agreements to explicitly include provisions for digital distribution and online promotion, enhancing the digital circulation of coproductions in streaming services.

References:

Albornoz, L. A. and Gallo, P. (2024). Global SVOD services in Spain: The availability and prominence of Spanish films and other audiovisual works. In C. Meir and R. Smits (Eds.). *European Cinema in the Streaming Era: Policy, Platforms and Production* (pp. 109–130). Palgrave Macmillan. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-42182-2_6.

Chalaby, J. K. (2023). *Television in the streaming era: The global shift*. Cambridge University Press. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1017/9781009199285>

Chalaby, J. K. (2025). The rise and fall of European media: EU policy in the streaming era. *European Journal of Communication*, 40(3), 266–283. <https://doi.org/10.1177/02673231251340801>

Dâmaso, M. (2025). (Ed.) *The European Union as a Global Cultural Power*. De Gruyter Brill. <https://doi.org/doi:10.1515/9783111026558>

Doyle, G., Paterson, R., & Barr, K. (2021). *Television production in transition: Independence, scale, sustainability and the digital challenge*. Palgrave Macmillan. <https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-63215-1>

European Producers Club, & CEPI. (2024). Statement in support of Brazilian independent producers regarding streaming regulation. https://www.europeanproducersclub.org/_files/ugd/93074a_92a1a698e76741859c3fd7638f563254.pdf

Fernandes, M. R. (2022). The end of an era? The decrease of the EU influence in Ibero-American digital media policy discourses. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 29(7), 876–893. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2022.2147517>

Fernandes, M. R. (2023). *Lost in transfer: Analysis of the media policy transfer from the European Union to Latin American supranational audiovisual spaces* [Doctoral dissertation, Vrije Universiteit Brussel]. ASP/VUB Press.

Fernandes, M. R., & Albornoz, L. A. (2023). Netflix as a policy actor: Shaping policy debate in Latin America. *Journal of Digital Media & Policy*, 14(2), 249–268.

https://doi.org/10.1386/jdmp_00124_1

Fernandes, M., Vlassis, A., Bissot, P., & Houard, S. (2025). The framings and strategies of cinema professionals: Report on “International Market” in the European Film Industry. Funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

García Leiva, M. T. (2025). *Audiovisual prominence and discoverability in Europe: Stakeholders’ alliances under construction*. *Convergence*, 31(1), 283–300.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565241260490>

García Leiva, M. T., & Albornoz, L. A. (2020). VOD service providers and regulation in the European Union: an audiovisual diversity approach. *International Journal of Cultural Policy*, 27(3), 267–281. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10286632.2020.1769614>

Idiz, D. R. (2024). Local production for global streamers: How Netflix shapes European production cultures. *International Journal of Communication*, 18, 2129–2148

Iordache, C., Raats, T., & Afilipoaie, A. (2022). Transnationalisation revisited through the Netflix Original: An analysis of investment strategies in Europe. *Convergence: The International Journal of Research into New Media Technologies*, 28(1), 236–254.

<https://doi.org/10.1177/13548565211047344>

Lobato, R. and Scarlata, A. (2022). Regulating Discoverability in Subscription Video-on-Demand Services. In T. Flew and F.R. Martin (Eds.). *In Digital Platform Regulation: Global Perspectives on Internet Governance* (pp. 209–228). Palgrave Macmillan.

Meir, C. and Mitrić, P. (2025). *Intellectual Property and the Contemporary European Audiovisual Industries* [Report]. European Audiovisual Production Association (CEPI).

<https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.2.20600.97282>

Smits, R. (2022). Circulation Patterns, Abundance and Scarcity: Film Availability in the Online Era. *Media Industries*, 9(2), 41-58. <https://doi.org/10.3998/mij.1875>

Smits, R. (2024). Theatrical Distribution or Online Streaming? Release Strategies in Europe in Times of Disruption and Change. In Meir, C. and Smits, R. (Eds.) *European Cinema in the Streaming Era*. Palgrave Macmillan, Cham. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-42182-2_5

Ulin, J. C. (2019). *The Business of Media Distribution: Monetizing film, TV, and video content in an online world*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781351136624>

Vlassis, A. (2016). Organizaciones regionales y diversidad cultural: la diplomacia de la Unión Europea con el Mercosur entre la sombra de Hollywood y la acción intergubernamental, *CIC. Cuadernos de Información y Comunicación*, 21, 97-115.

Vlassis, A. (2021a). Global online platforms, COVID-19, and culture: the global pandemic an accelerator towards which direction? *Media, Culture and Society*, 43(5), 957-969.

Vlassis, A. (2021b). European Union and online platforms in global audiovisual politics and economy: Once Upon a Time in America? *International Communication Gazette*, 83(6), 593–615. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748048520918496>

Vlassis, A. (2023). Platform governance and the politics of media regulation: the review of the Audiovisual Media Services Directive, *Journal of Digital Media & Policy*, 14(1), 29-46.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Policy Brief

January 2026

Developing the outreach and impact of European audience film awards

Authors: Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Introduction

Film awards are an essential component of the film industry. They indicate a film's quality and success and reflect the preferences of the awarding authorities, who are typically established film professionals. Thus, awards are often considered an important factor when evaluating the competitiveness of films and the European film industry as a whole (e.g., Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a; Abay et al., 2024; Simonton, 2009). They are also a means by which the authorities govern the industry, impacting the notions and perceptions of quality and novelty in the sector (Lähdesmäki & Hiltunen, 2026; Foret & Calligaro, 2019). However, awards presented by established professionals may distance the public from the award process and disregard their preferences. Nevertheless, the public can engage with the film industry and the negotiation of good films through audience film awards. Moreover, such awards have the potential to increase the visibility and audience of nominated and winning films, strengthening their competitiveness. The broader the audience engaged, the greater the positive impact. The European Union (EU) and the European Film Academy have recognised the potential of audience film awards, as demonstrated by the LUX European Audience Film Award and the Young Audience Award (YAA). Both awards are based on a broad, transnational audience vote for the best film. There are no other such broad, transnational audience film awards in the world.

LUX and YAA are categories of the European Film Awards, which are run annually by the European Film Academy. One of the major financiers of the European Film Awards is the European Union's Creative Europe programme, specifically its MEDIA strand. Furthermore, the LUX category has a direct link with EU policymakers, as half of the votes in the awarding process come from members of the European Parliament. The EU has a long history of awarding prizes in various cultural fields. These awards aim to highlight the European dimension of culture, promote European values and social goals, and strengthen the concept of a European cultural area in which cultural actors collaborate, and cultural products are consumed across national borders (Lähdesmäki, 2024). In addition to the cultural dimension, EU cultural prizes have an economic rationale, such as increasing the competitiveness of the European film industry in European and global markets (Lähdesmäki & Hiltunen, 2026). The power of cultural prizes stems from the attention they garner from various audiences. In the case of audience film awards, this power stems from public engagement in the viewing, reviewing, and voting processes.

This chapter approaches film awards as instruments for governing cultural and social goals and fostering competitiveness. It introduces these two awards and their awarding policies, discussing

their potential to engage European film audiences and increase the competitiveness of the European film industry. Based on the investigation of the awards, their awarding processes, and competitiveness (Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a; Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025b; Lähdesmäki & Hiltunen, 2026; Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2026), the chapter also identifies several weaknesses and lost potential. The chapter ends with recommendations for the European Parliament, the European Commission, the European Film Academy, and the various intermediary stakeholders involved in organising these awards suggesting improving the visibility, availability, and promotion of nominated films.

Young Audience Award

Awarding process and goals

The YAA was established in 2012 and has been awarded every year since. Initially, juries of young people aged 12–14 from European countries chose the winner from among three nominated films. Over the years, the number of countries involved has increased. In 2022, over 3,000 jury members from 42 European countries, as well as Israel, Palestine, and Australia voted for their favourite film. Juries watch the films in cinemas or online during uncommercial screenings organised by national partners of the European Film Academy, including film festivals, film centres, film agencies, and film educational organisations. In 2020, the Academy began developing the European Film Club in collaboration with young people. It is a platform that allows young people to discuss European cinema also outside of the competition. The platform became one way to participate in the voting, and it opened the competition to young people up to the age of 19.

The selection procedure for the nominated films has changed over the years, giving young people more agency. Until 2018, the nominees were directly chosen by five adult film experts. After that a small jury of young people chose the three nominees from films preselected by the experts. In 2022, for the first time young people participated in the pre-selection together with the experts (email correspondence with European Film Academy, 23 March, 13 April and 6 June 2023). In the final stage, the young audiences from around Europe form a broad jury that watches all three nominated films and vote anonymously.

Between 2012 and 2022, 40–60 films fitting the Academy's eligibility criteria were annually submitted to the YAA competition. The films must be full-length European productions, and the director must be born in Europe and hold a European passport. There are additional criteria for a *European film* based upon the Council of Europe Convention on Cinematographic Co-production (CETS No. 220). Eligibility requirements also include at least one of the following: previous awards, festival visibility,

or theatrical distribution in at least two European countries (European Film Academy, 2022; email correspondence with European Film Academy, 6 June 2023).

In addition to its core educational mission of promoting European cinema to young people, the YAA's general social aims include building bridges between cultures, facilitating peaceful exchanges of views, raising awareness of social issues, empowering young people, fostering a greater understanding of one's European neighbours, and offering the experience of being an active member of the European community.

Methodology and results

Our study aimed to understand what kind of youth films young people and film experts prefer and how the YAA has contributed to increasing the competitiveness of European cinema. First, thematic and style analysis of the 11 winning films was conducted to identify the films' key themes and their main stylistic characteristics. The features of the films were discussed in relation to previous studies on youth films and the film preferences of young people. The film analysis thus combined inductive qualitative analysis and theory-driven exploration. Second, data about the award was collected through desk research and by interviewing and discussing more freely with the representatives of the European Film Academy. This data and data about the winning films, such as admission numbers and the number of other awards received, were used to explore the recognition and impact of the award.

The thematic analysis identified three key themes: coming of age, belonging, and social challenges. The films dealt with various socially relevant and timely topics and brought out serious issues, such as bullying, impacting on the lives of young people. These themes are typical of youth films (Driscoll 2011), but stylistically the YAA films differed from popular youth films that are commonly adventurous and humorous. Based on the 11 YAA winning films, the study concluded that young people prefer realistic contemporary dramas, which are quite different from the action films they prefer according to earlier research (Soto-Sanfiel et al., 2018; 2021).

Because the analysis of the YAA revealed the central role of adults in the awarding process, it was concluded that the winning films reflect not only the preferences of the youth, but also those of the adult film professionals and the structure of the competition. If drama was the most typical genre of the films selected for the competition it is logical that many such films were awarded.

Regarding the potential of the YAA to promote European youth films the study concludes that the winning films have had very limited distribution in European countries. This may be improved with

the development of the European Film Club in the future. The award itself was found to be relatively unknown.

LUX

Awarding process and goals

In 2007, the European Parliament launched the LUX Film Prize as a symbolic gesture of its commitment to culture. For over a decade, Members of Parliament selected the winning film from a shortlist prepared by professionals and approved by the Committee on Culture and Education. In 2020, the award was rebranded as the LUX European Audience Film Award, and the European Film Academy, the European Commission, and Europa Cinemas began administering the award alongside the Parliament. Since then, nominees have been selected from films submitted to the European Film Awards. Winners are chosen through a 50/50 weighting of public votes and Member of Parliament ratings. With this change, the LUX became one of the 24 categories in the Academy's annual awards. Voting takes place on the LUX rating platform, with participation varying considerably. Around 45,000 ratings were submitted in 2023, about 22,000 in 2024, and nearly 33,000 in 2025 (Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a). These fluctuations illustrate the challenges and potential of engaging citizens in pan-European cultural initiatives.

Like other EU cultural awards, the LUX Prize blends cultural, social, and economic goals with political aspirations. It highlights European cinema as an art form and an industry while fostering cultural exchange and appreciation of Europe's diversity. Today, LUX stands out as one of the few transnational audience awards in which citizens from all 27 EU member states can vote for their preferred film. The award's eligibility rules emphasize both the European dimension and previous recognition. Films must be European, which is defined as being produced or co-produced in the EU or select non-EU countries, or involving professionals affiliated with them. Films must also have gained recognition at a major festival.

The award's value stems from its brand rather than its financial reward. Its financial support is channeled through translation. Nominated films are subtitled in all 24 official EU languages, and the winning film receives additional support in the form of adaptations for audiences with visual or hearing impairments. These measures aim to improve accessibility and distribution opportunities across Europe (Baschiera & Di Chiara, 2028; Stjernholm, 2026). The European Parliament created the award to increase the visibility of nominated films and help them reach audiences that might otherwise not have access to them (European Parliament, 2023). However, our study shows that such a wide reach is not always achieved (Lähdesmäki et al., 2025; Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a).

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Methodology and results

Our study had two aims. First, we used qualitative content analysis to explore the style and content of the winning films, determine their genres, and identify common themes. Second, we examined the effectiveness of LUX in enhancing the competitiveness of the winning films and how their competitiveness has evolved since LUX's establishment. Specifically, we examined how the transformation of the prize into an audience award impacted its ability to promote European film. Additionally, we compared the competitiveness of LUX-winning films to European films that have won more prominent film awards, such as the Palme d'Or and the Oscar for Best International Feature Film. We explored LUX's competitiveness by comparing extensive statistical datasets and conducting a correlation analysis of several economic and non-economic promotional indicators. These indicators included ticket sales and revenues, distribution and availability on video-on-demand (VOD) platforms, other film awards received, media recognition, and film ratings (Lähdesmäki et al., 2025; Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a). The sources used for data gathering were Box Office Mojo, The Numbers, the Lumiere database, the Lumiere VOD database, the Internet Movie Database, focus reports from the European Audiovisual Observatory, the International Index to Film and Television Periodicals/FIAF (ProQuest database), and the International Newstream (ProQuest database).

Our analysis of the style and content of LUX-winning films shows that they tend to be contemporary dramas dealing with serious social and societal issues. The transformation of LUX into an audience award did not significantly impact the content or style of the winning films.

The analysis of LUX-winning film competitiveness shows that an increase in one promotional indicator likely increases the others. However, some noneconomic promotional indicators did not consistently show a statistically significant correlation with the others. This suggests that economic and non-economic promotional indicators are not necessarily aligned (Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a). The findings suggest that the transformation of LUX into an audience award did not significantly impact its competitiveness.

A comparison with European Palme d'Or and Oscar Best International Feature Film winners shows that LUX winners are not competitive in the global or European film scenes. While the distribution of LUX winners was not poor, they underperformed in all other areas of promotion explored (Lähdesmäki et al., 2025; Hiltunen & Lähdesmäki, 2025a).

Policy recommendations

Exploring the two transnational European audience film awards yields useful findings for developing their award practices and improving their role in governing the European film industry and its competitiveness. Based on these findings, we recommend the following changes to enhance their outreach and impact.

- **Improve the promotion of both the YAA and the LUX Award:** Both awards should be promoted more effectively to increase their visibility to the public. The YAA has great potential to advance the youth film genre and the notion of young people as an important audience segment for European cinema. This potential can be realised through better public communication and promotion of the YAA itself and the awarded films. Currently, the LUX Award is promoted on the European Parliament's website and social media (Facebook) page, as well as on the websites of the selected cinemas arranging LUX Film Days screenings. However, these sites are not widely followed by the public. Other channels of promotion should be explored, because people cannot vote if they are unaware that such an award exists. Long-term support from the EU is needed to promote both awards.
- **Use the YAA more effectively to boost young people's engagement with European cinema:** The European Film Academy has already taken steps to expand the YAA initiative by enabling teenagers aged 15–19 to get involved via the European Film Club. The pedagogical material of the YAA could be developed into a European-level film literacy learning programme that utilises lessons learned from previous film literacy programmes created in European (see e.g., European Film Factory 2023) and national projects (see e.g., Mitric, 2022 for the Danish initiative of Med Skolen i Biografen/School Cinema and JEF n.d. for promoting film literacy in Belgium; EFAD n.d. for examples of national film education initiatives). Such programme could have cultural and social aims. An open-access research-based pedagogical learning programme could strengthen the platform and benefit various stakeholders more broadly, namely students and teachers in formal and informal educational institutions.
- **Make the nominated LUX films more widely available for viewing:** To encourage greater participation during the voting phase, the nominated films should be made more widely available. Screenings of the films should be organised in more cities, which would also allow for more effective local-level promotion of the award and the films. It would be worth exploring where else; besides Europa Cinemas Network cinemas, the films could be screened. For example, cultural institutions and educational establishments that already organise cultural events could be suitable venues for screening LUX films.

- **Improve the distribution and streaming of the awarded YAA and LUX films:** The YAA-winners have attracted mostly domestic audiences while the admissions in other European countries have been minimal. Better access via VoD platforms, or the European Film Club, could increase their recognition, as well as their social and economic impact. Improving the international distribution of the award-winning LUX films via cinemas and streaming services would also be beneficial. Currently, admission numbers for the LUX-winning films vary greatly. Resources should be invested in developing distribution strategies for these films.
- **Make the YAA films more accessible via translation:** YAA films could reach bigger audiences through multilingual subtitles and/or dubbing. It is recommended that the EU support this process, as it does with the films awarded the LUX Audience Film Award. Multilingual subtitling promotes linguistic and cultural diversity in Europe.
- **Emphasise LUX's aim to involve citizens:** LUX is one of the few audience awards in Europe. LUX should make this fact into an attraction. Currently, audience and European Parliament votes carry equal weight. However, given that the audience significantly outnumbers the Parliament's members, we recommend reconsidering the voting system. For example, in 2025, 33,000 ratings were given, whereas there are only 720 MEPs. Citizen participation could be strengthened by increasing the weight of the audience vote or even changing the award to be entirely audience-based.

References

Abay, F., Bengesser C., Damásio, M. J., Frühmorgen, T., Ibrus, I., Kostovska, I., Langgaard, K., Nielsen, J. I., O'leary, N., Olesen, J., Saluveer, S.-K., Materska-Samek, M., Talvik, R. J., Zemaityte, V. (2024). *State of European Film. An Overview of Key Industry Trends, Insights, and Policy Recommendations for the European Film and Audiovisual Industry*. CRESINE.

<https://kultura.irmo.hr/wp-content/uploads/2025/03/crescine-state-of-european-film.pdf>

Baschiera, S., & Di Chiara, F. (2018). The European Parliament projecting cultural diversity across Europe: European quality films and the Lux Prize. *Studies in European Cinema*, 15(2–3), 235–254. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17411548.2018.1442619>

CofE (2017). Council of Europe convention on cinematographic co-production (revised). Council of Europe Treaty Series No. 220. Rotterdam January 30, 2017. <https://rm.coe.int/168069309e>

Driscoll, C. (2011). *Teen film: A critical introduction*. Berg.

EFAD (n.d.). European Film Agencies. Film Education.

<https://europeanfilmagencies.eu/policy/working-groups/film-education>

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Email correspondence with Senior Project Manager Heidi Frankl, European Film Academy Productions. 23 March, 13 April, and 6 June 2023.

European Film Factory (2023). Cinema is the new school. <https://www.europeanfilmfactory.eu/>

European Parliament. (2023). LUX Audience Award. <https://lux-award.europarl.europa.eu/en/about>

Foret, F., & Calligaro, O. (2019). Governing by prizes: How the European Union uses symbolic distinctions in its search for legitimacy. *Journal of European Public Policy*, 26(9), 1335–1353. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13501763.2018.1523221>

Hiltunen, K. & Lähdesmäki, T. (2025a). The LUX Prize and the Challenges of European Film Competitiveness. *Studies in European Cinema*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17411548.2025.2572121>.

Hiltunen, K. & Lähdesmäki, T. (2025b). Young Audience Award. Parasta eurooppalaista nuortenelokuvaa, mutta kenen mielestä? *Kulttuurintutkimus*, 42(3), 38–55. <https://journal.fi/kulttuurintutkimus/article/view/141696>

Hiltunen, K. & Lähdesmäki, T. (Forthcoming 2026). The Young Audience Award: Cultivating Future Audiences for European Cinema. In K. Sarikakis, M. Dâmaso, T. Lähdesmäki, F. Ramos Arenas, & A. Vlassis (Eds.), *The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry: A Reader*. New York: Palgrave Macmillan.

JEF (n.d.). JEF for professionals. <https://professionals.jeugdfilm.be/en>

Lähdesmäki, T. & Hiltunen, K. (Forthcoming 2026). Governing the European Film Industry by Prizes: The European Film Awards and the LUX European Audience Film Award. In K. Sarikakis, M. Dâmaso, T. Lähdesmäki, F. Ramos Arenas, & A. Vlassis (Eds.), *The Governance of Competitiveness in the European Film Industry. A Reader*. Palgrave Macmillan.

Lähdesmäki, T., Hiltunen, K., Dâmaso, M., Behlil, M., Akçali, E. & Erdede, R. D. (2025). *Report on the Lux Audience Award & European Film Festivals*. Developed by the Horizon Europe project REBOOT (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Mitric, P. (2022). How does film education increase the economic and social impact of European arthouse cinema? The case of the Danish initiative Med Skolen i Biografen/School Cinema. *Studies in European Cinema*. Advance online publication.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17411548.2022.2115188>

Simonton, D. K. (2009). Cinematic success criteria and their predictors: The art and business of the film industry. *Psychology and Marketing*, 26(5), 400–420. <https://doi.org/10.1002/mar.20280>

Soto-Sanfiel, M., Villegas-Simón, I., & Angulo-Brunet, A. (2018). Youngsters and cinema in the European Union: A cross-cultural study on their conceptions and knowledge about cinema. *The International Communication Gazette*, 80(8), 714–745. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1748048518759171>

Soto-Sanfiel, M., Villegas-Simón, I., & Angulo-Brunet, A. (2021). Uses and consumption of cinema by European adolescents: A cross-cultural study. *Studies in European Cinema*, 18(2), 119–140.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17411548.2019.1613044>

Stjernholm, E. (2016). The European Union celebrates culture: The case of the European Parliament Lux Prize. *Studies in European Cinema*, 13(1), 19–31.

<https://doi.org/10.1080/17411548.2015.1135607>

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Policy Brief

January 2026

Towards a Unified European Policy Framework for Cinema/XR' Hybridization

Authors: Marcin Sobieszczanski, Asimina Koukou (UCA)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Introduction

Within the last 20 years, the audiovisual and film landscape worldwide has changed dramatically: once dominated by theatrical releases and a limited number of national film industries, cinema has evolved and reinvented itself to accommodate more interactive viewing experiences. Traditional film production, distribution and consumption are all undergoing major transformations with the advent of streaming and regional platforms, mobile devices and interactive media that have transformed film distribution, connection and interaction with audiences worldwide.

European cinema holds a distinctive position within this evolving environment. Historically, extensive public policy frameworks supported cultural diversity, national identities and linguistic plurality against the homogenizing market forces of globalization. Despite Hollywood's competition and international streaming platforms' challenges, Europe's policy frameworks-which are based on state subsidies, cultural exception principles, and co-production strategies-have allowed the European audiovisual industry to retain its strength.

The advent of Extended Reality (XR), which is an emerging umbrella term for all immersive technologies encompassing Virtual Reality (VR), Mixed Reality (MR) and Augmented Reality (AR) technologies, has marked a major change in contemporary media practices. XR technologies are not only revolutionizing the media landscape, but also the way in which people experience and create narratives. Regarding the film industry, XR opens countless new possibilities for film producers. It introduces a qualitative shift in audience behavior: from front-facing, mono-screen viewing to an experience that is more like an interactive and spatial one.

This policy brief argues that the hybridization of cinema and XR is a strategic opportunity for Europe, which is not yet sufficiently addressed by the existing policy frameworks. Although artistic experimentation and institutional recognition for emerging artists have increased, most public funding schemes and governance infrastructures continue to prioritize linear, screen-based film productions. Grounded in empirical research carried out by the REBOOT project, this work highlights the fragmentation, misalignment and imbalance of the European approach to cinema/XR hybridization in relation to existing eligibility criteria, cultural tests and mainstream funding schemes across diverse European countries. On an international level, Canada and South Korea make use of more coherent cultural and technological policy frameworks and integrate XR technologies into their national innovation programs. This policy brief supports an integrated European policy framework that fosters cinema/XR hybridization and frames it as a key cultural priority as well as a catalyst for future economic competitiveness.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

What Is Cinema/XR Hybridization and why is it important?

Cinema-XR hybridization is a specific form of media convergence where traditional film forms and techniques are combined with XR technologies to create an experience that is both interactive and multisensory. This blending of classic and immersive media attempts to transcend the passive nature of linear single-screen film experiences and expand films into spatial realms where cinematic aesthetics integrate with virtual environments, participatory engagement between creators and audiences and interactivity.

Historically, cinema has continually re-invented itself, reflecting technological advancements and societal changes. The journey of cinema began in the late 19th century with the introduction of narrative storytelling in films. The advent of sound in the 1920s has then transformed the entire production landscape which was then influenced by the emergence of color in films and their international expansion. Initial attempts of hybridization were then observable both through the development of innovative technologies in their prototype forms and through experimental practices within cinematic production. However, the materialization of early hybridization became more visible in the early 2000s with the development of industrial exhibition formats. Furthermore, the widespread adoption of Video on Demand (VOD) services since 2007, propelled by the ascendancy of major streaming platforms, has significantly contributed to the desertion of classical cinemas by audiences. This shift has been compounded by the fact that cinemas frequently find it challenging to offer a viewing experience that can adequately compete with the privacy and convenience afforded by home-based media consumption. Consequently, the cinematic landscape-and, more specifically, the processes of hybridization between cinema and XR technologies-has become increasingly fragmented and differentiated across countries. Contemporary manifestations of cinema/XR hybridization include 360° and spherical video works, immersive VR films, interactive cinematic narratives inspired by video game mechanics, and multisensory installations combining image, spatialized sound, vibration, haptics, and sometimes olfactory stimuli. Hybridization nowadays extends to immersive domes, XR-enhanced theatres, and mixed-reality performance spaces, where physical and virtual environments coexist.

Thus, cinema/XR hybridization is important for the film industry because firstly, it operates as a vehicle for the dissemination of widely distributed major productions, while not supplanting screen-based cinematic formats. In multiplexes constructed over the past decade, theatres employing hybrid formats coexist alongside those maintaining conventional projection methods. This coexistence contributes to the emergence of diverse viewing options, in which classical cinema screenings, interactive installations, and individual XR experiences all exist side-by-side. Secondly, cinema/XR hybridization transforms how audiences consume media and navigate across multiple

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

platforms and screens, blurring the boundaries between reality, cinema and immersive environments. In this context, audience attention and engagement are no longer defined solely by frontal framing and linear montage but are increasingly shaped by spatialized sound and user interactivity. These developments align cinema/XR hybridization with wider shifts affecting the global audiovisual ecosystem.

Therefore, understanding the dynamics of cinema/XR hybridization is of significant practical and policy relevance. European Union policies acknowledge the importance of immersive technologies within the cultural and creative industries through a range of frameworks aimed at strengthening innovation capacity, safeguarding cultural diversity, and reinforcing technological autonomy. Programs such as Creative Europe support the audiovisual sector's collaboration and exchange of knowledge among cultural institutions and artists across Europe and beyond, promote competitiveness, innovation, and sustainability. In parallel, policy initiatives related to Web 4.0 and Virtual Worlds, informed by the work of the European Virtual and Augmented Reality Industrial Coalition and the Action Plan for Media and Audiovisual, explicitly recognize immersive technologies as new ways of storytelling and as key factors in establishing competitiveness and technological sovereignty within Europe. As a result, immersive technologies increasingly feature in strategic policy narratives related to digital transition, competitiveness, and innovation. However, operational support remains dispersed across multiple programs and policy domains, with limited integration into core film funding structures. This work underlines the uneven and fragmented funding schemes of EU member-states and stresses the need for a more cohesive and harmonized policy approach. These arguments will be developed in the following sections.

Empirical Analysis: Evidence from the REBOOT Project

The empirical foundation of this policy brief is drawn from a multiscale comparative study aimed at identifying patterns, similarities, and differences across diverse national contexts, and at generating insights into how state aid has influenced the hybridization of cinema and XR technologies across regions. The analysis is based on a documentary review of state-aid schemes and policy instruments in five European Union member states (Belgium, France, Germany, Italy, and Luxembourg). Within Europe, Belgium and Luxembourg are notable for their exceptionally high rates of international co-productions, which make them central nodes in the networked structure of European film production. Their funding mechanisms and policy frameworks provide critical insight into the ways in which smaller countries can use cooperation and cross-border initiatives to stay competitive. Meanwhile, France, Germany and Italy are historically and structurally among one of the strongest film industries in Europe. As founding members of the EU, they have a mature and highly developed audiovisual sector, which is a traditional core of European film culture and political

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

leadership. Studies reveal how large, influential players adapt to-or sometimes-resist, emerging technological shifts such as XR. The analysis of the above countries provides a solid basis for examining the commonalities, correlations, and links between state aid in these regions.

The main funding bodies in the five EU member states are presented in Table 1. In Belgium, the *Centre du Cinéma et de l'Audiovisuel* (CCA) works along with regional organizations such as *screen.brussels* in providing film policy and funding. In France, the *Centre National du Cinéma et de l'Image Animée* (CNC) is responsible for the management of film, audiovisual and immersive production funding and support; in Germany, the *Federal Film Board* (FFA) offers funding at the federal level, complemented by a number of successful regional programs such as *Medienboard Berlin-Brandenburg* (MBB) promoting the regional film culture and industry. Italy has historically relied heavily on the *Ministry of Culture*, which is the principal funding institution supporting cinema and digital media; immersive projects gain visibility mainly through festival-based initiatives. In Luxembourg, the *Luxembourg Film Fund* plays a central role in supporting the industry's development by allocating financial aid across various stages of the creative process while in recent years, the Fund has notably intensified its support for animated films and extended reality (XR) projects, seeking to establish Luxembourg as a leader in immersive storytelling.

Country	Funding body	Policy emphasis	Structural limitations
Belgium	CCA / screen.brussels	Openness to innovation within general funding schemes	XR projects remain underrepresented and marginal
France	CNC	Dedicated support for immersive projects across development stages	Funding remains modest compared to mainstream cinema
Germany	FFA / MBB	Targeted support for innovative audiovisual and XR projects	Strong regional presence, fragmented national coordination
Italy	Ministry of Culture	Festival-based initiatives recognizing immersive works	Lack of dedicated national funding and centralized data
Luxembourg	Film Fund Luxembourg	Diversified portfolio including XR projects	Small-scale productions shaped by national priorities

Table 1: Selected national policies and initiatives facilitating the hybridization of cinema and XR examined in the REBOOT project.

The comparative analysis reveals a high degree of similarity in the structure of film funding schemes across the European states analyzed-particularly in their use of direct subsidies (national/federal

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

versus regional/community and automatic versus selective funds) and fiscal incentives (Table 2). However, important divergences emerge in terms of strategic emphasis and policy priorities. Certain states place greater focus on territoriality, using funding mechanisms to anchor production activities within national or regional borders, whether through inward investment conditions or local spending requirements. Others foreground the cultural dimensions of funded projects, incorporating criteria related to language, national identity, or gender equity. Most of the EU states under research assess film projects through structured cultural tests and eligibility criteria, which play a central role in determining eligibility for public funding. Cultural tests evaluate either the cultural content of the production or co-production, or the geographical location, the nationality of the producer, the language of the film or the professional basis of the producer being located in the respected countries.

Country	Funding body	Direct public funding	Indirect public funding (fiscal incentives)
Belgium	Centre du Cinéma et de l'Audiovisuel (CCA)	Yes	Tax Shelter
Germany	Filmförderungsanstalt (FFA)	Yes	German Federal Film Fund (DFFF – rebate)
France	Centre national du cinéma et de l'image animée (CNC)	Yes	SOFICA; Crédit d'Impôt Cinéma; Crédit d'Impôt Audiovisuel
Italy	Ministry of Culture	Yes	External Tax Credit; Producers' Tax Credit; International Tax Credit
Luxembourg	Film Fund Luxembourg	Yes	Audiovisual investment certificates / tax benefit allowing reduction of taxable income (CIAV-type regime)

Table 2: Selected EU-level audiovisual and digital policies pertinent to cinema/XR hybridization examined in the REBOOT project.

Regarding the investment in XR projects, this work additionally reveals a fragmented and polarized funding scheme across Europe. While countries such as Belgium (screen.brussels), France (CNC), Germany (via MBB), and Luxembourg (Luxembourg Film Fund) have established dedicated mechanisms to support immersive content, others-such as Italy-continue to concentrate predominantly on traditional film and television formats through institutions like the *Ministry of Culture*. The data shown in Table 3 reveals a marked asymmetry between EU member states. Disparities are evident both in terms of total financial support allocated (in euros) and the number of

funded projects, with significant variation in scale and intensity across national funding systems. For *Brussels*, data notably demonstrate out of a total of 29 projects granted funding in 2023 only 3 were VR productions. While immersive productions are present in the Brussels-capital region, they remain significantly underrepresented when compared to more traditional formats (14 feature films, 8 documentaries, 4 animations and 3 live action series). In *France*, the amount dedicated to immersive creation was €3.6 million for a total of 103 projects. Even though the funds are enough, they remain relatively modest when compared to the budget for a single large-scale film production (€5-10 million). According to the annual activity report of MBB in *Germany*, the region of Berlin funded a total of 21 XR/IAC (Innovative Audiovisual Content) projects, allocating €2.5 million to immersive and interactive works. This included €1.1 million for 6 XR games and €1.4 million for 15 innovative audiovisual content projects. The funded works were actively represented at major international film festivals, including Cannes and Venice, underlining both the artistic caliber and the global visibility of Germany's immersive sector.

For the case of *Italy*, the Ministry of Culture does not provide comprehensive or publicly accessible data. However, more detailed insights are available through the *Venice Gap-Financing Market*, an initiative organized under the *Biennale di Venezia* as part of the *Venice Production Bridge*. In 2023, this platform reported support for 14 immersive works, several of which were structured as international co-productions, notably involving partners from Germany and Quebec. To conclude, *Luxembourg's* investment in immersive technologies (8 XR projects in 2023) illustrates a clear ambition to position itself as a competitive player in the evolving global content market. Through financial support for XR initiatives, the country is fostering a dynamic and sustainable audiovisual sector capable of adapting to the challenges of the global film economy. Its strategy reflects a broader European tendency to integrate technological innovation into cultural production, with a focus on audience engagement and new forms of storytelling.

Country	Funding body	Immersive projects funded	Allocation
Belgium	Screen.brussels	3 VR projects	No data
France	CNC	103 immersive creation projects	€3.6 million
Germany	Medienboard Berlin-Brandenburg (MBB)	21 XR/AI projects (6 XR, 15 AI)	€2.5 million
Italy	Ministry of Culture	No data	No data
Italy	Biennale di Venezia	14 XR projects	No data

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Italy	Ministry of General Contemporary Creativity (Digital & Green Investment)	1,860 projects	€108 million
Luxembourg	Film Fund Luxembourg	8 XR projects	No data

Table 3: Selected financial assistance and financed immersive initiatives examined in the REBOOT project.

When comparing XR production trends between Northern and Southern European member states, a notable distinction emerges: Northern countries—including Germany, France, Belgium, and Luxembourg—have established robust, often well-funded ecosystems for immersive content development. These nations benefit from a combination of long-standing cultural funding policies, strong digital infrastructures, international networking capacity, and dedicated XR funding lines (e.g. *screen.brussels*, *Medienboard Berlin-Brandenburg*, CNC, and Luxembourg Film Fund). These structures allow for experimentation and early adoption of immersive technologies, reinforced by access to EU-level instruments such as *Creative Europe MEDIA* and collaborations with global partners. By contrast, Southern European countries—with the Italian case as a core example—have tended to prioritize more traditional film and television formats in their national funding agendas. While there are emerging efforts to embrace digital and green transitions (based on the data by the *Ministry of General Contemporary Creativity*), immersive projects still represent a marginal share of the total audiovisual output. Limited institutional specialization, fragmented data collection, and a slower integration of XR-specific funding mechanisms contribute to this disparity. This North-South divide reflects broader asymmetries in technological infrastructure, institutional agility, and access to innovation funding. It also mirrors discrepancies in how cultural innovation is positioned within national development strategies. While Northern states increasingly frame XR as a pillar of digital sovereignty and soft power, Southern states are still consolidating their foundational support systems before fully embracing immersive formats.

The Case for a Unified Policy Framework for Cinema/XR Hybridization in Europe

Addressing the imbalances outlined above will require considerably more than just isolated investments. The European Union must act as a whole to realign EU policies and establish a unified and cohesive European policy framework for cinema/XR hybridization. Such a framework should not be interpreted as being about increasing the degree of centralization or homogenizing existing national policies. It is rather about the degree to which national policies can be aligned to each other (existing national systems), coordinating the various levels of governance (national and regional), and modernizing the tools of policymaking so that they reflect today’s reality of the audiovisual sector.

There are countries that have established successful models of integrating cultural/technological policymaking from which the European Union can learn important lessons. Canada for instance has

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

developed a significantly integrated strategy. Canadian policies explicitly support XR production as part of broader national objectives for competitiveness agendas, with substantial public investment not only in content creation but also in infrastructure, research, and international market expansion. Through federal and provincial initiatives such as Telefilm Canada and the Canada Media Fund, funding is allocated to projects that explore interactive narratives and technological innovation. Critically, Canadian policymakers do not perceive XR as a niche creative sector, but rather as an essential component of a wider digital strategy closely aligned with economic growth, cultural diplomacy, and technological sovereignty.

Similarly, the European Union can learn much from the South Korean case in developing and implementing a national vision linking culture, technology and global competitiveness. Through state-supported initiatives such as the Korean Film Council (KOFIC) and the Korea Film Commission and Industry Network (KFCIN), the country has actively integrated XR and immersive media into its mainstream audiovisual policies. National strategies explicitly support the production of VR, AR, and XR content through direct grants, equipment subsidies, and the development of XR infrastructures, including immersive theatres and specialized creative hubs. Furthermore, South Korea's cultural policy adopts a holistic approach, integrating cinema, gaming, and interactive media, and recognizing that the future of storytelling will be inherently hybrid and multi-platform. Unlike the fragmented national funding systems observed in Europe, South Korea's approach is nationally coordinated and globally oriented, thereby securing a leading position in the evolution of the global audiovisual ecosystem.

Drawing on these examples, a coordinated and unified European strategy could consolidate existing fragmented approaches by combining key elements of all the current EU policies (cultural, digital, innovation) into a single cohesive framework. By integrating cultural and innovative strategies, promoting cross-border collaboration, and by coordinating funding and governance efforts, this framework could produce synergies among objectives that are currently pursued independently. An integrated strategy of this type would provide several benefits-it would facilitate collaboration easier, promote more effective use of public funds, and enable the European Union to position itself as a global leader in the XR film industry in cinema/XR hybridization by leveraging its cultural diversity, public funding capacity, and creative talent base.

Conclusion and Recommendations

As stated, the European Union has prioritized the promotion of emerging technologies and the advancement of innovation within its cultural and creative industries. However, this study has demonstrated clear disparities in both the accessibility and implementation of VR/AR/XR

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

technologies across the European continent. To foster a more coherent cinema-XR hybridization and to align state and private support policies, the following recommendations are proposed:

Firstly, it is imperative to increase the overall volume of XR funding, with the explicit aim of enabling the coexistence of traditional and immersive technologies within audiovisual production. Enhanced funding would foster experimentation, encourage technological integration, and support creators working across multiple formats. At present, significant disparities exist among EU member states: while countries such as Germany and France offer relatively well-structured programs (characterized by high production quality but limited in financial scope), others such as Belgium and Italy lag in terms of systemic support for immersive works. A coordinated pan-European effort is therefore necessary to ensure that creators in all member states can access the financial and technical resources required to innovate in this field.

Secondly, there is an urgent need to standardize and harmonize public and private funding frameworks for immersive and XR projects across Europe. A more unified regulatory and financial structure would not only simplify the application process and increase transparency for creators but also reduce the funding inequalities that currently separate well-resourced countries from those with minimal XR investment. Harmonization would also facilitate cross-border collaborations, creating an environment where European creators can cooperate more easily and benefit from shared infrastructures and joint financing mechanisms.

Lastly, the study considers the fact that younger creators are often more receptive to immersive technologies, and thus emerging technologies should be integrated into higher education curricula. Universities and film schools must play a key role in shaping a skilled and adaptable workforce, capable of navigating and innovating within a rapidly evolving audiovisual landscape. By investing in technological literacy, interdisciplinary training, and production-oriented education, Europe can position itself as a global leader in the XR film industry, ensuring that future generations of filmmakers are not only technologically proficient, but also creatively empowered.

Taken together, these measures outline a vision in which cinema/XR hybridization is not treated as a peripheral innovation, but as an integral component of Europe's audiovisual future. By adopting a unified and cohesive policy framework, Europe can transform current challenges into opportunities, fostering a cinema that is technologically adaptive, culturally grounded, and capable of sustaining its relevance in a rapidly changing global media landscape.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

References

Bizern, C., & Autissier, A.-M. (1998). *Public aid mechanisms for the film and audiovisual industry in Europe: Comparative analysis of national aid mechanisms*.

Bomnüter, U., & Schulze, A. (2019). Governance of the German film industry: A multilevel analysis of state aid policy. *International Journal of Arts Management*, 22(1), 54–72.

<http://www.jstor.org/stable/45221738>

Bordwell, D., Staiger, J., & Thompson, K. (1985). *The classical Hollywood cinema: Film style and mode of production to 1960*. Columbia University Press.

Centre national du cinéma et de l'image animée. (2020, October 15). *The National Centre for Cinema and Moving Images (CNC) develops new means to promote the French image industry*.

https://www.cnc.fr/web/en/news/the-national-centre-for-cinema-and-moving-images-cnc-develops-new-means-to-promote-the-french-image-industry_1580634

Centre national du cinéma et de l'image animée. (2024). *Bilan 2023: Cinéma, audiovisuel, vidéo, jeu vidéo*.

Cucco, M. (2018). The vertical axis of film policies in Europe. In N. Mingant & C. Tirtaine (Eds.), *Reconceptualising film policy* (pp. 263–275). Routledge.

Direzione generale Cinema e Audiovisivo. (2024). *Italy offers everything you need: Funds, tax credits and co-productions*.

Direzione generale Cinema e Audiovisivo. (2024). *Italy's cinema and audiovisual industry in numbers – 2023*.

European Audiovisual Observatory. (2016). *Public financing for film and television content: The state of soft money in Europe*. Author.

European Audiovisual Observatory. (2019, May). *Mapping of film and audiovisual public funding criteria in the EU*. <https://rm.coe.int/mapping-of-film-and-audiovisual-public-funding-criteria-in-the-eu/1680947b6c>

European Audiovisual Observatory. (2023, December 12). *Mapping of film funds – Belgium (BE)*. <https://rm.coe.int/mapping-film-funds-be/1680aed573>

European Commission. (2009, February 7). *Communication from the Commission concerning the State aid assessment criteria of the Commission communication on certain legal aspects relating to cinematographic and other audiovisual works (Cinema Communication) of 26 September 2001*. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52009XC0207\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52009XC0207(01))

European Commission. (2013). *Communication from the Commission on State aid for films and other audiovisual works (Text with EEA relevance)*. *Official Journal of the European Union*, C 332, 1–11. [https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013XC1115\(01\)](https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:52013XC1115(01))

European Commission. (2020). *Action plan: For the strategic approach to the EU's media and audiovisual policy* (Press release IP/20/2250). https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/api/files/document/print/en/ip_20_2250/IP_20_2250_EN.pdf

European Commission. (2020). *Media and audiovisual action plan*. European Union.

European Commission. (n.d.). *Creative Europe programme – Performance*. https://commission.europa.eu/strategy-and-policy/eu-budget/performance-and-reporting/programme-performance-statements/creative-europe-programme-performance_en

Film Fund Luxembourg. (2024). *Co-producing with Luxembourg*. <https://filmfund.lu/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Coproducing-with-Luxembourg-web-version-1.pdf>

Film Fund Luxembourg. (2024). *Rapport annuel 2023*. https://filmfund.lu/wp-content/uploads/2024/10/Rapport_Annuel_2023.pdf

Guerrini, L. (2024, December 1). *It has become harder to make films in Italy: All about the reform that will also be limiting foreign productions*. *NSS Magazine*. <https://www.nssmag.com/en/lifestyle/39028/reform-public-funds-italian-cinema-new-rules-criticism>

Meloni, G., Paolini, D., & Pulina, M. (2018). State subsidies to film and their effects at the box office: Theorizing and measuring why some genres do better than others. In P. C. Murschetz, R. Teichmann, & M. Karmasin (Eds.), *Handbook of state aid for film: Finance, industries, regulation* (pp. 99–117). Springer.

Messerlin, P., & Vanderschelden, I. (2018). France's protected and subsidised film industry: Is the subsidy scheme living up to its promises? In P. C. Murschetz, R. Teichmann, & M. Karmasin (Eds.), *Handbook of state aid for film: Finance, industries, regulation* (pp. 311–333). Springer.

Morton, L. H. (1992). El cine del futuro: The cinema of the future. *Presence: Teleoperators and Virtual Environments*, 1(3), 279–294. <https://doi.org/10.1162/pres.1992.1.3.279>

Murschetz, P., Teichmann, R., & Javed, S. (2019). State aid for film and audiovisual services: A synoptic review of key principles and governance models in Europe and abroad. *América Latina*, 8, 181–200.

Orankiewicz, A. (2022). The role of public support for the film industry: An analysis of movie production incentives in Europe. *Prace Naukowe Uniwersytetu Ekonomicznego we Wrocławiu*, 66(2).

Stelmach, M. (2024). Cinema counts: The computational turn and quantitative methods in film studies. *Kwartalnik Filmowy*, 127, 6–28.

Vohra, M. (Ed.). (2025). *Introduction to extended reality (XR) technologies*. John Wiley & Sons.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Policy Brief

January 2026

The European Union as an Enabler of International Film Relations

Authors: Mafalda Dâmaso, Anna Niutta (EUR), Antonios Vlassis, Marina Rossato Fernandes (ULIEGE), Luis Albornoz, Isabela Vargas Miranda, M^a Trinidad García Leiva (UC3M), Tuuli Lähdesmäki, Kaisa Hiltunen (JYU), Ruken Doğu Erdede, Melis Behlil, Elif Akçalı (KHAS)

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Core Problem

The cultural action of the European Union (EU) beyond its borders is framed by the Joint Communication Towards an EU Strategy for international cultural relations (ICR; European Commission, 2016), which places long-term trust-building through mutually beneficial and equal cooperation (not only among professionals but also with audiences) at the core of the EU's global cultural action. However, the practical ties between this policy and initiatives to support the film industry – European and otherwise – beyond the EU's borders remain incipient. An exception lies in the annual European Union Film Festivals (EUFF), although REBOOT's research also shows that there is scope to strengthen EUFF's ties with ICR. At the same time, European and non-European film professionals repeatedly call for increased opportunities to exchange knowledge, co-produce, and better engage with their audiences, echoing the principles behind the ICR framework.

This policy brief makes policy proposals to strengthen the links between the EU's film policy, both internal and external, and the EU's International Cultural Relations. This would strengthen the impact and sustainability of both policies, maximising public investment, and reinforce their ability to respond to the needs of film professionals in Europe and beyond. At the same time, it would also support the production and distribution of independent film in Europe and abroad, increasing the circulation of unique stories that reflect multiple world views.

The policy proposals are organised around the following dimensions: co-productions, film festivals, skills/knowledge exchange and capacity development, diplomatic activities and European film funding schemes.

Methodology

This policy brief results from findings from several REBOOT resources: the report on the LUX Audience Award & European Film Festivals (D3.1; Lähdesmäki et al, 2025) and concomitant policy brief (Ramadani et al., 2025), the report on the mapping and EU law of institutional models for the promotion of the EFI (D3.5; Vlassis et al, 2025), the report on the framings and strategies of cinema professionals (D4.1; Rossato Fernandes et al. 2025), and the report on international understanding of the European film industry (D4.4; Dâmaso et al, 2025). The brief combines and adapts policy recommendations made in some of these reports (D3.1 and D4.4) and insights connected to ICR that emerge from other reports (D3.5 and D4.1). Altogether, it reflects the views of more than 1000 stakeholders.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Regarding report D3.1, its aim was to understand the rationale and organisational challenges behind the EU Film Festival (EUFF). It drew on desk research, feedback from organisers in 27 countries collected by Cineurope in 2023, and qualitative content analysis of semi-structured interviews with 19 interviewees representing European External Action Service (EEAS) officials and festival organisers in eight non-EU countries hosting the festival in 2023. This research was translated into a policy brief (Lähdesmäk et al., 2025). As for report D3.5, it mapped institutional models for the promotion of the EFI and was divided into several parts. Part A aimed to understand the institutional promotion efforts of national film industries in eight EU Member States (MS). The study drew on extensive desk research and 72 semi-structured interviews with European film professionals conducted between September 2023 and November 2024. Report D4.1 aimed to understand how European film professionals perceive competitiveness, how they interact with international markets, and what challenges and opportunities the film industry faces. It resulted from a survey distributed across European countries, which collected 432 responses between November 2024 and February 2025, and 37 in-depth semi-structured interviews with EU film professionals, conducted between January and August 2024. Moreover, participant observation was conducted during the 77th edition of Locarno Film Festival in 2024. Finally, report D4.4 on the international understanding of the European film industry is based on data collected through 99 semi-structured interviews with key informants conducted from December 2023 to July 2025, and a common international survey conducted across six international markets, which collected 425 valid responses between November 2024 and March 2025.

Discussion

These reports reveal several common challenges shared by EU and non-EU stakeholders (ranging from film professionals, cultural and film institutes to film festival organisers and EU delegations), which can be addressed with the collaborative framework that characterises International Cultural Relations. Although such challenges overlap, they are presented separately for analytical reasons.

Co-productions are highly valued by film professionals and other industry stakeholders, who highlight their cultural, industrial and financial benefits. However, the data indicate the need to adapt them to recent and ongoing changes in the film industry caused by technological advances and market dynamics such as the increasing power of international streamers. This requires both structural and financial readjustment of existing public policies and support. Furthermore, countries from the Global South have fewer financial and industrial resources to participate in co-productions and this requires an approach that is tailored to their needs and particularities. Additionally, information on co-productions is fragmented and difficult to understand, and the procedures for carrying out co-productions are often overly bureaucratic.

As for film festivals, a challenge that was commonly mentioned by stakeholders relates to the participation of European professionals in non-European festivals and vice versa due to insufficient funds. This is combined with the high screening fees charged by sales agents, which significantly limit the presence of European films in regions such as South America. Furthermore, independent producers, both from within and outside the EU, struggle to gain visibility at major festivals. With regard to festival design, professionals from EU and non-EU countries alike believe that the number of side events should be increased and that these should focus on dialogues that foster collaboration and encourage professional networking. Another important issue was raised by South African professionals: the marginal positioning of non-European pavilions at European film festivals. When it comes to festival communication and evaluation, increased emphasis on values such as inclusivity, diversity, and representation is needed. Finally, the cultural and social benefits of festivals are not always evaluated, especially through non-market indicators.

Regarding the exchange of skills/knowledge and capacity development, respondents identified fragile or insufficient distribution channels that promote cultural exchange inside and outside the EU as a top challenge and priority. Moreover, the lack of an overarching framework for distribution and promotion is seen as hindering the internationalisation of independent films.

Concerning audience engagement, the need to enable film professionals and organisations to invest in long-term audience building with specific groups (such as the youth) was also identified. Finally, other issues with negative impact across the supply chain were also highlighted, such as the significant barriers that non-EU professionals face in accessing EU archives.

EU diplomatic activities are valued and considered essential to support international cooperation. However, EU stakeholders highlighted the limited funding and institutional capacity to focus on such work and the need for increased coordination between EU Member States as well as greater alignment of funding programmes. Non-EU professionals from the Global South recognised the importance of EU frameworks for cultural cooperation but emphasised the need to include non-EU professionals in strategic decisions. Moreover, the need for greater cooperation between EU and non-EU public streaming platforms was raised.

Finally, stakeholders call for distribution and promotion to be recognised as an important component of the film industry. The need for this change is evident in the fact that European film funding schemes dedicated to distribution have been abandoned and that the scope of existing European networks does not always include distribution and promotion.

Implementing the following Policy Recommendations would address these challenges and needs.

Policy Recommendations

Co-productions

Co-production agreements and funding

- **Reinforce existing funding available to support international co-productions, including with third countries:** International productions need funding for promotion and distribution to increase their availability and visibility in European and non-European countries (D4.4). Funding should encourage collaboration and prioritise small-scale projects with local professionals (D3.1).
- **Update international co-production agreements:** Co-production agreements enable the internationalisation of films and provide an opportunity to share knowledge. Non-European professionals believe these agreements should be updated to reflect changes in the industry, such as shifts in market dynamics and the increasingly dominant presence of streaming services (D4.4).
- **Develop common funding schemes, legal agreements, and professional networks of cooperation to strengthen EU/non-EU co-productions:** EU professionals emphasise the need for reinforced institutional support for co-productions with non-EU countries. The EU could develop institutional partnerships to facilitate such collaborations (D4.1).
- **Lower thresholds of co-production financing requirements:** Respondents from the Global South state repeatedly that co-production financing requirements are too high to be met by national budgets. Lowering such thresholds could increase the number of co-productions with Global South partners (D4.4).

Information about co-productions and their implementation

- **Lower bureaucratic burdens:** International co-production agreements should be simplified and standardised into clearer procedures. Moreover, assessment of co-production collaborations could be made on the basis of artistic and technical contributions, rather than solely financial ones. In addition, procedures should be more flexible for countries facing political and financial instability (D4.4).
- **Consolidate and make information accessible in a dedicated website:** Information about co-production agreements is scattered across different websites and provided in multiple languages. Foreign film professionals find it hard to access comprehensive detailed information about the legal, financial, and technical requirements necessary to access the agreements. This represents a problem especially for industry newcomers, who need this information for the first time and are unfamiliar with the technical requirements of co-

productions. To address this issue, the EU could create a cohesive website that is easy to access and to understand and offer it in multiple languages (D4.4).

Film festivals

Access to film festivals by European and non-Europeans film professionals

- **Support the participation of EU film professionals in non-EU festivals and market events.** This would make it easier to build networks with professionals from non-EU film industries and help establish or strengthen ties with local audiences (D4.4).
- **Reinforce and widen existing funding towards the participation of non-European film professionals:** According to interviewees, funding to participate in festivals is either only available to very few participants or does not fully cover their expenses. To ensure more international participation in European film festivals, the EU could establish dedicated funding for professionals from selected international markets (D4.4).
- **Create funding schemes to cover or subsidise screening fees for selected European films, allowing them to take part more easily in international film festivals outside Europe:** This would allow festival organisers in South America to select EU films based on their quality and audience appeal and to not be as constrained as they currently are by the high fees demanded by sales agents (D4.4).
- **Improve two-way exchange:** Support the establishment of agreements between EU and non-EU film festivals/markets. This would strengthen the selection of EU/non-EU local films at non-European/European film festivals, creating new distribution channels for such films and promoting cultural exchange (D4.4).
- **Increase funding for Cineuropa and EU Delegations:** The EU could increase funding for Cineuropa and EU Delegations to promote cultural diversity globally through a higher number of films in the former's repository and at EU Film Festivals, and to cover costs in low-income markets (D3.1).

Film festival design

- **Strengthen dedicated workshops and events in co-production forums and markets:** Film festivals provide opportunities to expand professional networks. The EU could provide funding to festival organisers to increase the number of workshops and events dedicated to international co-productions. Moreover, funds could be allocated to invite more European and foreign financiers to attend small to medium-sized festivals (D4.4).
- **Support networking events at film festivals:** Respondents describe festivals as an important platform to connect professionals with the industry (D4.1). Establishing strong networks could help in developing coordinated strategies and foster knowledge exchange.

- **Develop tailored audience engagement:** Develop strategies to engage both existing and new audiences, particularly when they include film students and other film experts, and adapt the festivals' design to reflect these engagement goals (D3.1).
- **Revise the positioning of non-European pavilions in European film festivals:** Respondents deem the presence of an African pavilion in European film festivals as very important. However, they also describe it as often being located in a marginal place, reflecting unbalanced treatment for European and non-European film professionals. To address this issue, European film festivals could rearrange the location of non-European pavilions (D4.4).
- **Strengthen opportunities for two-way exchanges and highlight side events of the EUFF:** Refocus the design of the EUFF to more effectively and systematically foster two-way exchanges between EU and non-EU film professionals, by:
 - Transforming side-events into dialogues that would support co-learning, collaboration and co-productions, and using films as a platform to discuss shared challenges;
 - Reinforcing support for visits by non-EU professionals to EUFF and to European festivals;
 - Supporting the screening of non-EU films at EUFF and at film festivals in Europe to promote balance and inclusion (D3.1).

Film festival communication

- **Communicate EUFF objectives continuously:** To foster consensus and a sense of shared ownership, highlight mutuality, and avoid instrumentalism, the EUFF should clearly communicate its objectives to EU Member States and other stakeholders (D3.1).
- **Reinforce diversity and representation in the communication materials of the EUFF and other film festivals:** Ensure that communication materials align with societal values such as inclusivity and diversity. (D3.1).
- **Focus on shared values:** Emphasis should be placed on shared values rather than on "EU values" to avoid the perception of a neo-colonial approach (D3.1).

Film festival evaluation

- **Consider broader indicators in film festival implementation and monitoring:** To avoid a short-termist analysis of data collected, incorporate non-quantitative and non-market indicators to measure cultural and social outcomes of the EUFF. This also applies to the evaluation of the implementation of other film festivals and in Cineuropa's collection of information (D3.1).

Skills/knowledge exchange and capacity development

- **Provide greater support to independent arthouse European and local exhibitors of European and non-European film** by:
 - Supporting independent arthouse film exhibitions in Europe and non-European markets with joint skills/knowledge exchange and/or capacity development schemes;
 - Strengthening local exhibition rights of European films;
 - Increasing MEDIA funding for dubbing and subtitling and extending it to non-EU exhibitors (D4.4).
- **Invest in marketing and long-term audience building from an early stage** by:
 - Developing cultural programmes aimed at non-European youth combining European and non-European film screenings (D4.4);
 - Supporting marketing and audience engagement strategies tailored at multiple and diverse groups from an early stage of the production process (D.4.1).
- **Reinforce international promotion efforts through dedicated support to international sales agents** by:
 - Promoting the planning of a film's commercial exploitation from the moment of its conception (D4.1);
 - Promoting relations between European producers and international sales agents (for example, through the organisation of forums) so that the marketing strategy for a film is thought of and defined at the early stages of the project (D4.1; D4.4).
- **Increase support for the distribution of EU/non-EU co-productions within and beyond the EU.** While co-productions allow films to circulate across the participating countries, there is no overarching European framework guiding distribution and promotion strategies on an international and global scale (D4.1)
- **Facilitate access to film archives by non-European stakeholders:** Several non-European respondents describe difficulties in accessing European archives due to high access fees. The EU could recommend that national archives reduce access costs for film professionals and organisations from low- and middle-income countries (D4.4).

Diplomatic activities

- **Include non-Europeans in film funding evaluation committees:** Some respondents pointed out that decisions on funding for collaborations between the Global South and the EU are made by people who are unfamiliar with the local culture. Including non-European film professionals on the evaluation committee could ensure more informed decisions (D4.4).

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

- **Develop new partnerships among publicly managed windows of exhibition:** Strengthening collaboration between the bodies that manage public exhibition windows in non-European countries could increase European films circulation (D4.4).
- **Develop new partnerships among publicly managed streaming services:** Similarly, respondents from various case studies highlighted the need for more cooperation between publicly operated non-European streaming platforms such as CineAr Play (Argentina), Nuestro Cine MX (Mexico) and Tela Brasil (Brasil) and their European counterparts. Such cooperation would strengthen the exchange of European and non-European titles and open up new exhibition opportunities for both sides (D4.4).
- **Support increased coordination between EU and Member States (MS) funding schemes:** When there is alignment between EU transnational audiovisual goals and national foreign priorities, reinforce existing support to allow for stronger coordination of EU and MS activities celebrating shared values (MS, EU, non-EU countries) and cultural diversity (D3.5).
- **Frame the EUFF within broader public diplomacy efforts:** Place more emphasis and provide clearer guidelines for festival organisers on the international cultural relations approach in the implementation of the EUFF (D3.1).

European film funding schemes

- **Revive film programmes dedicated to distribution and exhibition:** Given the growing challenges in distributing and screening European films, the EU could consider restoring the Europa Cinema Mundus programme, which supported film programming between MEDIA and non-MEDIA member countries, or the MEDIA Mundus programme, which offered funding for distribution, promotion, and co-production with non-European countries (D4.4). Besides funding, such programmes should also include training and networking opportunities to help international distributors combine local market expertise with innovative release strategies and make better use of the funds provided.
- **Develop coherent cross-border film circulation strategies:** EU film professionals describe fragmented approaches to distribution, promotion, and marketing efforts that are linked to their national contexts. The EU could address this issue by supporting the development of common strategies to reinforce the international circulation of a selected number of European and non-European independent films (D4.1).
- **Expand networks such as European Film Promotion (EFP):** respondents described the limited scope of EFP in relation to the challenges facing the EFI (D4.1). Its expansion could create institutional capacity to implement the previous recommendation.

REBOOT resources

D4.4: Dâmaso, M., Niutta, A., Vargas Miranda, I., Albornoz, L. A., García Leiva, M.T., Rossato Fernandes, M., Vlassis, A., Behlil, M., Doğu Erdede, R., Akçalı, E. (2025). The Framings and Strategies of Cinema Professionals. Report on International Understandings of the European Film Industry. Developed by the Horizon Europe project REBOOT (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16744614>

D4.1: Fernandes Rossato, Marina, Vlassis Antonios, Bissot Pauline, Solenn Houard (2025): The Framings and Strategies of Cinema Professionals. Report on "International Market" in the European Film Industry, funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769. <https://orbi.uliege.be/bitstream/2268/335660/1/REBOOT%20D4.1%20-%20FINAL.pdf>

D3.1: Lähdesmäki, T., Hiltunen, K., Dâmaso, M., Behlil, M., Akçalı, E., & Doğu Erdede, R. (2025). Report on the Lux Audience Award & European Film Festivals. Developed by the Horizon Europe project REBOOT (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17241275>

Ramadani, G., Chatziefrimidou, A., Sarikakis, K., Sganga, C., Turan, P., Lähdesmäki, T., Dâmaso, M., Hiltunen, K., ERDEDE, R. D., Akcali, E., Behlil, M., Albornoz, L. A., García Leiva, M. T., Vargas Miranda, I. M., Biltereyst, D., Ramos Arenas, F., Willems, E., & Caballero Ruiz de Martín-Esteban, L. (2025). Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M24. The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14778271>

D3.5: Vlassis, A., Bissot, P., Houard, S., Dâmaso, M., Niutta, A., García Leiva, MT., Albornoz, L. A., Vargas Miranda, I., Andriopoulou, I., Turan, P., Pilo, P., Glowacki, M., Mikucki, J., Hiltunen, K. (2025). Promotion of the EFI at the international level: Institutional and policy models across the EU Member States. In: Vlassis, A. Psychogiopoulou, E, Kandyla, A. and Sarikakis, K. (Eds.). (2025). Final report on the mapping and EU law of institutional models for the promotion of the

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

EFI. Developed by the Horizon Europe project REBOOT (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme (Grant Agreement No. 101094769).

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15781266>

References

European Commission (2016). Joint Communication from the European Union and the High Representative “Towards an EU strategy for international cultural relations. <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=JOIN%3A2016%3A29%3AFIN>.

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union’s Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Disclaimer

This document is part of the outputs of the *Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness - REBOOT* project, which received funding from the Horizon Europe programme of the European Union under the Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

© 2026, REBOOT Consortium. All rights reserved. Licensed to the Horizon Europe under conditions.

Licence

This document is authorised under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International (CC-BY 4.0) unless otherwise noted. Reproduction and distribution of the material for research, educational or other non-/ commercial purposes is permitted without the authorisation of the rights holders, provided the source is properly acknowledged.

Please see: <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>

Citation

Please cite this report as follows:

Sarikakis, K., & Haslauer, S. (Eds.). (2026). *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36*. The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Please cite each Policy Brief as follows:

Sarikakis, K., Zogo, Y. S. C., Arkoumanis, G., Baumgartner, S., Haslauer, S., Ramadani, G., & Chatziefraimidou, A. (2026). Framing AI Legal and Ethical Frontiers in the European Film Industry. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 7–14). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Amram, D., Fortuna, J., Patti, N., Punzo, V., Romano, R. (2026). Children's rights in the digital era: take-away policy recommendations for the film industry. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 15–25). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Fernandes, M. R., Vlassis, A., Albornoz, L. A., Vargas Miranda, I., García Leiva, M. T., & Dâmaso, M. (2026). Streaming services and the competitiveness of the European Film Industry in Europe and Latin America. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 26–37). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Lähdesmäki, T., & Hiltunen, K. (2026). Developing the outreach and impact of European audience film awards. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 38–47). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Sobieszczanski, M., & Koukou, A. (2026). Towards a Unified European Policy Framework for Cinema/XR Hybridization. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 48–60). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Dâmaso, M., Niutta, A., Vlassis, A., Fernandes, M. R., Albornoz, L. A., Vargas Miranda, I., García Leiva, M. T., Lähdesmäki, T., Hiltunen, K., Erdede, R. D., Behlil, M., & Akçalı, E. (2026). The European Union as an Enabler of International Film Relations. In K. Sarikakis & S. Haslauer (Eds.), *Policy briefings deriving from WP2-5 M36* (pp. 61–71). The REBOOT Project (Reviving, Boosting, Optimising and Transforming European Film Competitiveness – REBOOT), funded by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No.101094769. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18258831>

Contact

Website: www.thereboot-project.eu

Email: reboot.2023@univie.ac.at

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

REBOOT Contributors

universität
wien

ΕΛΙΑΜΕΠ
ELIAMEP

UNIVERSIDAD
COMPLUTENSE
MADRID

KADIR HAS
ÜNİVERSİTESİ

Erasmus
University
Rotterdam

UNIVERSITEIT
GENT

uc3m

Universidad Carlos III de Madrid
Instituto Universitario del Cine Español

Sant'Anna
School of Advanced Studies - Pisa

UNIVERSITÉ
CÔTE D'AZUR

JYVÄSKYLÄN YLIOPISTO
UNIVERSITY OF JYVÄSKYLÄ

UNIVERSITY
OF WARSAW

REBOOT (www.thereboot-project.eu) has received funding from European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No. 101094769.

